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Research Report: Work Package 3.2

Michael Roberts, Lara Band, Wes Forsythe, Deanna Groom, Rory Quinn, Sarah Saunderson and Phoebe Wild

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1.1 Authors and Acknowledgements

Authors

Dr Michael Roberts¹ - Co-I/Work Package Lead (Marine Geoscientist)
Dr Rory Quinn² - Co-I (Marine Geoscientist)
Dr Wes Forsythe² - Co-I (Maritime Archaeologist)
Dr Julian Whitewright³ - Collaborator (Senior Investigator (Maritime))
Lara Band¹ - Research Officer (Maritime Archives)
Deanna Groom¹ - Research Officer (Maritime Archives)
Sarah Saunderson¹ - Research Officer (Maritime Archives)
Phoebe Wild¹ - Research Officer (Maritime Archives)
Dr Peter Robins¹ - Research Fellow (Physical Oceanographer/Modeller)
Soizic Garnier¹ - Research Officer (Physical Oceanographer/Modeller)

Acknowledgements

Dr Innes McCartney¹ - Research Fellow (Marine Archaeology)
Cathy Blakey¹ - Data Librarian
Gwyn Roberts¹ - Computer Manager
Ahmed Ali¹ - Software Analyst/Developer
Adrian Corkill⁴ - Maritime Historian (Isle of Man)
Michael Lowrey⁴ - Naval Historian (North Carolina, U.S.A.)
David Wilson⁴ - Historian (Isle of Anglesey)

¹ School of Ocean Sciences, Bangor University

² School of Geography and Environmental Sciences, Ulster University

³ Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales

⁴ Independent Researcher/Contributor

1.2 Introduction

The aim of Unpath'd Waters Work Package 3.2 'Science and the Sea' was to investigate ways of enhancing our current understanding of Underwater Cultural Heritage (UCH) by integrating marine scientific data with the historic record and maritime related collections. Using the Irish Sea as the principal setting with a smaller, more focussed study area located to the west of the Isle of Man (IOM) known to contain several unknown wrecks and missing vessels as an 'Unpath'd Waters Project Pilot', our aims were to:

- Integrate scientific data (principally multibeam sonar) with maritime archives (loss records, vessel plans, newspaper reports etc) to increase the proportion of identified and confirmed wrecks in the study area.
- Apply scientific data at regional and local scales to develop a preservation potential model quantifying and incorporating risk factors to aid in the prediction of site-specific development trajectories.
- Utilise marine collections and maritime archives to develop new/novel narratives focussed on vessels newly identified/confirmed through this research or listed as missing in the study area.
- Develop novel applications for combining marine scientific data with the historic record to improve knowledge and management of UCH.

The offshore, shelf sea marine environment, generally characterised by water depths ranging from 30m to 250m contains a significant proportion of our collective maritime heritage, principally in the form of sunken vessels. It has been estimated that the world's oceans and seas may contain more than three million shipwrecks, spanning thousands of years of human history, development and endeavour. From a national perspective, the UK's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) contains more than 9800 charted wreck sites (UK Hydrographic Office open licence data 2021), most of these sites have been surveyed and documented at least once since the widespread introduction and application of sonar survey technology in the early 1970's. However, the surveys and data acquired at each site over the last fifty years varies substantially in terms of date range, survey type, data quality and resolution and consequently a significant proportion (>30%) of wreck sites in the UK EEZ remain classified as 'unidentified' or 'unknown'.

Between 2012-2023 Bangor University, utilising hull mounted high-resolution multibeam echosounders (MBES), surveyed 583 shipwreck sites located in the Irish Sea region. Data from 273 of these surveys underpinned a study whereby the effectiveness of combining maritime archives with structural attributes derived from individual wreck surveys to determine wreck identities at a regional scale, within a specific geographical area was

investigated (McCartney 2022). The study demonstrated that as well as vessels classified as 'unknown', a significant proportion of wrecks have been incorrectly identified. There is no indication to suggest that similar situations would not be encountered in other offshore regions within the UK EEZ and further afield. The research demonstrated that confidence in shipwreck identification could be significantly enhanced by combining wreck attributes derived from high resolution MBES with relevant historical archives, provided that 100% of charted wreck sites within any defined study area had been subject to MBES survey. This research resulted in 67 previously unknown wrecks (24.5%) being identified and 62 wrecks (22.7%), having their identities revised, i.e. 47.2% of the total sample set being identified/revised.

A substantial amount of marine survey in the Irish Sea has also been undertaken via the Irish Government funded 'Infomar' programme, which has primarily (although not exclusively) focussed on areas within the Irish EEZ and resulted in the acquisition of multibeam sonar data coverage from over 480 wreck sites, many of which are located in the Irish Sea, adjacent to and in areas associated with research undertaken within this work package.

Initially and currently to a significant extent, wreck sites are primarily examined from a navigational safety perspective, i.e., to establish the presence and precise location of an anomalous/irregular feature or object on the seabed and to determine the level of risk it poses to contemporary marine traffic. However, recent years have also witnessed a dramatic increase in the use of offshore sites in relation to the installation, commissioning and maintenance of communication and energy infrastructure and in relation to this, there has been growing demand to improve knowledge and management of Underwater Cultural Heritage (UCH) assets within areas scheduled for development. Additionally, advances in seabed survey technology, coupled with an increase in survey activity have also led to growing concerns related to the potential 'toxic legacy' shipwrecks may pose to marine wildlife and the nearshore marine environment.

Science and the Sea has attempted to extend the previous Irish Sea study area further north to encompass a new, more focussed study area, situated to the west of the Isle of Man (IOM) which contains over 122 charted wreck sites. Bangor University's research vessel Prince Madog surveyed 80 of these sites in August 2020 and resurveyed 18 of these together with 42 new sites in April 2023, the resultant data has provided the Unpath'd Waters project team with a unique opportunity to further refine this field of research (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: IOM study area and charted wreck sites surveyed in 2020/23.

1.2.1 The Irish Sea and Isle of Man study area

The Irish Sea, bounded by the land masses of Ireland and the United Kingdom, is relatively sheltered and open to the Celtic Sea in the south and the Malin Sea in the north. General depths in the central Irish Sea range from between 80m to 200m with coastal regions open to the shelf off the west coast of Ireland and the Celtic Sea. It consists of the deeper 300km long and 30-50km wide north-south orientated St George’s Channel to the west, with shallower embayments to the east. As this channel is open-ended, it receives Atlantic Water and influences from the north through the North Channel and from the south via the Celtic Sea and St. George’s Channel. Two large islands are located to the east of the main channel, the Isle of Man and Anglesey (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Bathymetric variation in the case study 1 study area. The case study 2 area around the Isle of Man is highlighted by the red polygon. Bathymetric data: EMODnet.

Demands are placed on the Irish, Malin and Celtic Seas by the high population densities of Northwest Europe, with pressures on the environment arising from fishing, trade, industrial and urban waste, hydrocarbon extraction, and the more recent development of offshore renewables and leisure activities (Sharples and Holligan, 2004). Away from coastal regions and fluvial inputs, the Irish shelf seafloor comprises a layer of mobile sediments, predominantly reworked glacial and postglacial sediments (Van Landeghem et al., 2009). Over most of the region, semi-diurnal tides are the dominant physical process, propagating into the Irish Sea from the Atlantic Ocean through the North Channel and St. George's Channel (Howarth, 2005). Tidal range varies from 10m in Liverpool Bay on the largest springs, to regions of very small tidal range at amphidromic points near Arklow (Howarth, 2005). Surficial sediment type reflects the distribution of tidal stress, with the coarsest sediments (gravel and sand) associated with the strongest tidal currents off the west coast and in the central Irish Sea and North Channel. In the weaker tidal regions and on the Malin Shelf, the seabed comprises sand and mud, with a large depositional centre in the western Irish Sea (Western Irish Sea Mud Belt), where deeper water and weaker tidal currents have resulted in the accumulation of approximately 40m of Holocene mud (Coughlan et al., 2021).

A pronounced seasonal cycle in temperatures distribution in the Irish Sea results from vertical exchanges and heat input at the surface (Howarth, 2005). The annual mean temperature varies between 10 and 11°C, coolest in February and March and warmest in August. Salinity decreases from 35ppt at the southern end of St. George's Channel to 34ppt in the North Channel (Howarth, 2005).

Whilst the wrecksite preservation potential research focussed on a regional scale, encompassing the Irish Sea as a whole, a polygon defining an offshore area in the northern

Irish Sea extending between the Isle of Man and Northern Ireland containing 125 charted wreck sites was selected as a focussed study area for the wreck identification research. This more focussed study area was defined by the availability of a recently acquired multibeam data set obtained in 2020.

1.3 The Irish Sea Wreckscape: An Historical Summary

Julian Whitewright and Michael Roberts

It is no exaggeration to say that the Irish Sea is full of shipwrecks. Its location as the main north-south seaway up the western side of Great Britain, and with shorter east-west routes to and from Ireland mean that archaeological evidence for seafaring in the Irish Sea dates to prehistory. In later periods, coastal shipping routes, fishing and longer distance voyages to-or-from ports like Liverpool, Belfast, Dublin, Cardiff, Swansea or Bristol added further layers of seafaring activity linked to increasingly global systems of trade and communication.

Figure 3: UKHO Wrecks & Obstructions within the Irish Sea.

The vast majority of the voyages that took place in the Irish over the past few millennia ended successfully with a boat being beached in a sandy cove, or a ship entering a small harbour, or in more recent centuries a sophisticated port complex. Yet, despite the undoubted knowledge and expertise built up by seafarers in the Irish Sea, the vagaries of weather, technical failure, or just sheer bad luck have resulted in many shipwrecks. By way of illustrating the extent of what can be termed the Irish Sea 'wreckscape' the UK Hydrographic Office (UKHO) lists c. 3,000 wrecks and obstructions in its database for the area (Fig. 3).

Many of the vessels lost, especially from the earliest periods will probably never be found. The numbers of known wrecks can only ever be a small portion of the overall numbers of

losses. Arriving at an accurate figure of total losses is impossible, primarily because of the lack of reliable reporting of instances of shipwreck prior to the post-medieval period. Even then, it is only from the 1700s that shipping losses and shipping records become reliable enough to be statistically useful.

At the same time, we need to remember that the loss of a ship, or boat, is unlikely to take place in a way that respects modern boundaries, borders or the jurisdictional remit of heritage agencies. Shipwrecks have happened, and the borders have been drawn afterwards. As a result, taking full account of a corpus of shipwrecks, both physical and documentary, within a sea area that is split across national and international boundaries is challenging. This is even truer when differences in the assembly and curation of the maritime elements of National Monuments Records are considered (see Chapter on The National Records); different NMRs have recorded shipwrecks and shipping losses in different ways, at different times, for different reasons.

Providing a historical overview of the Irish Sea wreckscape is therefore challenging. The approach adopted here is simply to use a single national dataset as our vessel for exploring and explaining things. While inevitably imperfect, there is more certainty over consistency within the context of a single set of records. With this in mind, the shipwreck data held within the National Monuments Record of Wales (NMRW) is utilised here. This dataset lies within the Irish Sea in its widest sense, is large enough to be statistically useful, while also being manageable in terms of its overall numbers. It also has wider Unpath'd Waters links through its use as a training dataset for the Unpath'd Waters Work Package 2 (see Chapter 9: Artificial Intelligence and Record Enhancement).

The Welsh territorial sea area within the Irish Sea is one that has been used since the earliest times. There is evidence for prehistoric settlement along the Welsh coast, giving indirect evidence for prehistoric seafaring activity. In south-east Wales fragments of Bronze-Age boats have been found at Caldicot, followed by the Romano-Celtic vessel from Barland's Farm. Evidence for Viking-Age voyaging exists in the place names around the coast of west Wales, and in a sword-hilt found far offshore on the Smalls reef. The archaeological remains of medieval vessels have been recorded in the Menai Straits at Pwll Fanog and recovered from Magor Pill in Gwent. Most spectacularly of all, the Newport Medieval Ship remind us of the great size that sea-going ships could reach in the periods before the loss of such vessels was well recorded. The range of vessels briefly summarised also indicates the spread of ship-types, sizes and purposes that we should always hold in mind when imagining watercraft in the past. Ships and boats often developed specialist forms and/or functions to fulfil their specific niche within the maritime elements of a society.

The records of shipping losses from the post-medieval period, and especially the 1700's onwards very much reflect this variation in size, shape and activity. Documented losses and known wrecks of ships within the NMRW were assessed as part of Work Package 2, to extract the ship-type from the available written description, using an automated computer process. The results fall into two overall categories. The first is where the type of vessel is recorded in non-specific terms, and which describes an action or activity. For example, 'cargo vessel' or 'passenger vessel' in relation to what was being carried, or 'fishing vessel' or 'pilot vessel' to describe what was being done. The second is a reference to a specific type of ship such as those listed in shipping registers or casualty loss records, for example a schooner, smack, or sloop. The commonest types in each category are shown in Table 1, but it is

instructive to note that overall, 106 different ship-types exist within the NMRW, even allowing for the broad-brush nature of the analysis.

Non-Specific		Specific		Wrecks	Wreck %
Craft	954	Schooner	927	42	5%
Cargo Vessel	339	Sloop	457	6	1%
Packet	179	Screw Steamer	346	149	43%
Pilot Vessel	72	Smack	331	2	1%
Trawler	65	Brig	219	5	2%
Collier	58	Barque	195	29	15%
Fishing vessel	49	Ketch	162	5	3%
Tug	44	Brigantine	134	9	7%
Passenger vessel	39	Full-Rigged Ship	83	12	14%
Ferry	20	Flat	82	3	4%

Table 1. Commonest Non-Specific and Specific vessel-types listed within the NMRW as identified during Unpath'd Waters Work Package 2.

Table 1 provides us with an impression, and only an impression, of the nature, range, and scope of maritime activity being undertaken in the Irish Sea. The non-specific category illustrates the range of reasons and differing rationale with which people set sail in the past. Meanwhile, the specific category gives an insight, especially within the period from the late 18th to early 20th century of the range of ship-types that might be engaged in the movement of goods, people and ideas around, across and along the Irish Sea. This is important, because our focus, perhaps naturally, when considering a wreckscape, is to think about the obvious; the large, often well-preserved iron and steel wrecks of screw-steamers found in deeper water. Coexisting alongside those are the remains of a myriad of other vessels, sometimes only surviving in the form of a cargo mound, such as the many slate wrecks along the North Wales coast, or in the wooden wrecks buried within the inter-tidal zone. It is of note within Table 1, that 43% of the vessels identified as screw steamers in the NMRW are associated with a wreck, but that only 5% of schooner losses are associated with a corresponding set of archaeological remains. On an even more specific basis, 13 out of the 16 U-Boat/Submarine losses (not shown in Table 1) within the NMRW are wrecks, rather than documented losses. Of course, wooden wrecks exist in deep water, but their survival is much harder to gauge and their remains, often more broken up than their iron and steel counterparts are much harder to detect.

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of Schooners, Screw-Steammers, Barques and Flats within the NMRW.

Focusing on the distribution of four ship-types (Fig. 4) provides a useful oversight of the differences that might be expected across the rest of the Irish Sea. This illustrates the loss locations, either a wreck, or a historical record of loss, for Schooners, Screw-Steammers, Barques, and Flats. The differences in distribution and underlying reasons for such differences are instructive. As the commonest ship-type in the NMRW schooners have a distribution all around the Welsh coast, as well as at many offshore locations. Their distribution again reminds us of the key role that these medium sized ships played in facilitating trade and transport during the 19th century, and by extension, the importance of local, and medium distance voyages in general. By contrast, Barques are the commonest large ocean-going, long-distance sailing ship in the NMRW, and have a distribution largely confined to north and south Wales, representing the likely arrival/departure ports of these vessels, Liverpool in the north, and Cardiff or Swansea in the south. In addition, their locations of loss are mainly coastal with only a few offshore records. In many cases the record of loss is for a ship being driven ashore, resulting in a distribution in shore along the coast. By contrast, screw-steamers are represented by a high number of offshore locations, with a distribution that covers most of the sea area. It should be noted that many of these ships were sunk by U-Boats in the first and second world war, rather than through being wrecked or foundering in the more traditional sense. Finally, the inclusion of Flats allows consideration of regional patterns within the wreckscape. These vessels were notable for their part in the trade along the north Wales coast and around Liverpool Bay, and their distribution within the NMRW is strikingly reflective of this.

A detailed analysis of data from 273 multibeam surveys of charted offshore wreck sites (wrecks in water depths greater than 20m) collected by researchers at Bangor University from the central Irish Sea region and further analysed in McCartney 2022, indicates that vessels lost during WWI constitute the majority of vessels in the Irish Sea (fig. 5), however a significant proportion of recorded/charted sites were also found to be unidentifiable or have been miss-identified as wrecks (i.e. ballast mounds, geological features, vessel debris or 'rough ground').

Figure 5: Classification of identified wreck sites.

Such a brief sketch is very much one of the potential of maritime archaeological remains within Wales, and by extension the rest of the Irish Sea area. Everything has the potential to exist within the archaeological record of the Irish Sea wreckscape, from prehistoric watercraft, through to 20th century steel wrecks. The incomplete nature, in terms of what has been found, merely reflects the potential of what is still to be found through future surveys or following sediment movement on beaches and estuaries. The nature of much of the seafaring activity that has taken place in the past dictates that we should not expect distinct or different patterns in different jurisdictions. The differences are likely to be the result of our own record keeping, or the way in which those records have been assembled. Often, we are often only able to comment on the general nature of things, as here, for example noting the prevalence of schooners as the commonest ship-type within the NMRW. But, at times it is possible to link fully together the specifics of a shipwreck, the historical documentation of that vessel and its crew, and the circumstances of its loss.

Within the UnPath'd Waters project, such linkages are explored within a series of case studies from the northern part of the Irish Sea, around the Isle of Man, where the UnPath'd Waters project has sought to provide new identifications and information about the shipwrecks located there.

1.4 Case Study 1: Wreck Formation Processes, Risk Assessment and Wreck Trajectories in the Irish Sea

Rory Quinn

1.4.1 Introduction

A principal task for this work package was to investigate the preservation potential of Irish Sea wrecks, with a view to underwater cultural heritage (UCH) management. As UCH is a finite resource, it is important to understand the risk historic wreck sites are under in response to increasing anthropogenic and natural forcing. Human impacts typically include trawling and ocean engineering (subsea cables, pipelines, turbines), while physical, chemical and biological processes acting in the water column and seabed naturally deteriorate wreck sites. Climate change is magnifying these natural effects. We use acoustic remote sensing to locate and identify wreck sites and use the resultant data to build high-definition digital models of the wrecks. When combined with environmental variables, we can model the preservation potential of these wreck sites and assess potential risks. The main modelling technique we use to investigate site formation, risk and future trajectories is weighted overlay modelling (also termed multi-criteria analysis).

Shipwreck site formation research encompasses the processes by which wreck sites are created and preserved (Oxley and Keith, 2016) and provide valuable insights into the factors that influence the formation and preservation of wrecks and associated artefacts (Gregory et al., 2024). Post-depositional site formation processes are those that affect long-term site preservation. These are commonly divided into natural processes (N-transforms), caused by the ambient physical, chemical and biological processes occurring in the natural environment and cultural processes (C-transforms), related to human intervention (Oxley and Keith, 2016).

In this study we use a combination of key N- and C-transforms (Table 2) to model site formation, risk and site trajectories of shipwrecks in the Irish Sea.

Data	Source	Reference	Resolution	Unit	Averaging
Depth	EMODnet	EMODnet (2022)	Multiscale	M	-
Sediment	EMODnet	EMODnet (2022)	Multiscale	Folk 7 class	-
Temperature	BioOracle v.2.0	Assis et al. (2017)	9.2 km at equator	°C	2000-2014
Dissolved oxygen	BioOracle v.2.0	Assis et al. (2017)	9.2 km at equator	µmol/L	2000-2014
Salinity	BioOracle v.2.0	Assis et al. (2017)	9.2 km at equator	-	2000-2014
Current velocity	BioOracle v.2.0	Assis et al. (2017)	9.2 km at equator	m/s	2000-2014

Fishing intensity	EMODnet	EMODnet (2022)	5.5 km	h/km ² /month	2015-2018
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Table 2. Summary of the open-source data used in the modelling.

1.4.2 Data sources

Data analysis was conducted in QGIS v3.16 Hannover and incorporated data from two portals (Table 2): EMODnet (<http://emodnet.eu>) and Bio-ORACLE (<http://www.bio-oracle.org>). The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) consists of more than 160 organisations assembling marine data, products and metadata to make these fragmented resources more available to public and private users relying on quality-assured, standardised and harmonised marine data which are interoperable and free of restrictions on use. Bio-ORACLE is a set of GIS rasters providing marine environmental information for global-scale applications (Tyberghein *et al.*, 2012). The original Bio-ORACLE project contained surface data. In 2017 Bio-ORACLE v2.0 was released, containing benthic layers (Assis *et al.*, 2017), which have been incorporated into this project. Models produced with benthic layers are more meaningful than their surface equivalents when studying the preservation of archaeological materials on the seafloor.

Two national shipwreck databases were used in the analysis. Data for the Republic of Ireland were sourced from the INFOMAR Project, a DECC funded joint programme between the Geological Survey Ireland and the Marine Institute, surveying the unmapped marine territory off Ireland. The wreck sites contained in this database have all been surveyed using multibeam echosounders:

<https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/3f2815ec89e745d2b65630429d06385c/> Data for the UK were downloaded from the Admiralty Marine Data Portal: <https://datahub.admiralty.co.uk/portal/apps/sites/#/marine-data-portal/items?tags=GlobalWrecks>

Figure 6. Flow chart of the methodology used to derive the weighted overlay models.

1.4.3 N-transforms and C-transforms used in modelling

Depth (N-transform)

Depth (Fig. 7) is considered to influence the preservation state of wrecks, with deep water wrecks generally believed to survive in better condition than similar vessels in shallow water. Deep wrecks tend to survive longer than shallow wrecks, as they are partially isolated from anthropogenic influence and generally experience lower energy environments.

Figure 7: Bathymetric variation over the study area. Bathymetry data: EMODnet.

Substrate (N-transform)

Sediment type (Fig. 8) influences the preservation of archaeological material; generally fine-grained sediment offers more protection and preservation potential than coarse sediment. Substrate is arguably the most important variable in assessing site formation, as substrate controls many of the other environmental variables. Bottom type has chemical and immediate physical effects on wreck material, controlling burial of archaeological material and therefore access of oxygen, seawater and sulphate-reducing bacteria to wrecks. Every sediment is a mixture of grains of varying sizes. A common classification used derives from that proposed by Folk (1954). It groups grains into mud, sand and gravel on the basis of their diameter with the boundary between mud and sand size grains at $63\mu\text{m}$ (0.063mm) and the boundary between sand and gravel size grains at 2mm (Long, 2006). The relative proportion of the grains in the three categories is then used to describe the sediment. The EMODnet sediment reclassification scheme includes seven seabed substrate classes (Folk 7) at a scale of 1:100k. Six substrate classes are defined on the basis on the Folk triangle (mud, sandy mud, muddy sand, sand, coarse sediment, mixed sediment) and one additional substrate class (rock and boulders) is included by the project team.

Figure 8: Substrate data in the Irish Sea. Substrate data: EMODnet.

Benthic current velocity (N-transform)

The energy regime at the seafloor is a significant factor controlling the stability and preservation of archaeological material. Currents exert shear stresses on the seafloor (Fig. 9), and archaeological material resting upon it.

Figure 9: Mean benthic current velocity. Data: Bio-Oracle v2.0.

Benthic temperature (N-transform)

Water temperature (Fig. 10) is an important variable in determining the rate of marine growth, corrosion of metal objects and the bio-deterioration of organic material (McCarthy, 2000).

Figure 10: Mean annual benthic temperature. Data: Bio-Oracle v2.0.

Salinity (N-transform)

Water salinity (Fig. 11) has a pronounced effect on the stability of metal objects, ceramics, and biological growth (McCarthy, 2000), e.g. controlling the environment favoured by bacteria and fungi that have a marked effect on the deterioration of wood.

Figure 11: Mean annual benthic salinity (Bio-Oracle v2.0).

Benthic dissolved oxygen (N-transform)

Oxygen availability (Fig. 12) influences the preservation potential of metal and wooden wrecks. For example, wooden parts of shipwrecks tend to be well-preserved only when exposed on the seabed to water with low oxygen content (e.g. Eriksson and Rönby 2012) or when buried in dysoxic and anoxic sediments.

Figure 12: Mean annual benthic DO (Bio-Oracle v2.0).

Bottom fishing intensity (C-transform)

Maximizing social and economic benefits from fisheries and protecting UCH are management goals often viewed to be at odds with each other. Some researchers argue that wrecks are heavily impacted by commercial fishing practices (Brennan et al., 2016), others appear less convinced (Parham, 2017; Hickman, 2024). The main pressure on submerged wrecks from commercial fishing is defined by the physical abrasion of the seabed by bottom-contacting fishing gear. Figure 10 shows the total fishing effort for otter trawls in the Irish Sea (2015–2018) as an example. The *Nephrops* fishery in the Irish Sea west is economically the most important in this geographic area. *Nephrops* is a burrowing species, found in the North Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea at depths of 10–1200 m, and constructs and inhabits extensive burrow complexes in suitable muddy sediments (Campbell et al., 2009). These characteristic fine-grained habitats are therefore targeted by commercial fishers in the Irish Sea.

Figure 13: Otter trawl intensity in the Irish, Celtic and Malin Seas (2015-2018). Fishing intensity data: EMODnet.

1.4.4 Multi-Criteria Analysis Modelling

Preservation potential models were developed in QGIS v3.16 using the ‘Weighted Multi-Criteria Analysis’ plugin (Plugin ID 2069), using the environmental variables outlined above (Table 2). Four preservation potential models were developed using C- and N-transforms (Table 3).

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Substrate	100%	50%	50%	14%
Depth	-	-	-	14%
DO	-	-	10%	14%
Salinity	-	-	10%	14%
Temperature	-	-	10%	14%
Velocity	-	-	20%	14%
Fishing intensity	-	50%	-	14%

Table 3: Variable weighting used in preservation potential modelling scenarios: model 1 for buried material; model 2 for semi-exposed material; model 3 for fully exposed material; model 4 all variables equally-weighted.

Model 1: UCH buried completely beneath the seabed

Model 1, the most basic of all four models, assumes the preservation potential of material buried beneath the seabed is dependent upon substrate conditions. The variable weighting

is therefore 100% substrate (Table 3). In most environments the seafloor itself is the most important factor in influencing the potential decay or preservation of a submerged shipwreck (Keith and Evans, 2016). The thickness and composition of seabed sediments, coupled with hydrodynamic processes that move sediments, determine whether a shipwreck becomes entirely or partially buried or remains exposed on the seabed (Keith and Evans, 2016).

Model 2: UCH semi-exposed at the seabed

Model 2 assumes the preservation potential of semi-exposed and shallow buried material is dependent upon substrate conditions and seabed fishing intensity. For example, the *Nephrops* fishery in the Irish Sea west is economically the most important in ICES Division VIIa and is mainly prosecuted by vessels from UK (Northern Ireland) and Ireland. This fishery occurs throughout the year and does not exhibit major inter annual changes in seasonal pattern (AFBI, 2020). Furrow marks from *Nephrops* fishing gear (otter doors) typically bite 20 cm into seabed. The variable weighting in this model is: 50% substrate and 50% fishing intensity (Table 3).

Model 3: UCH fully exposed at the seabed

Model 3 assumes the preservation potential of fully submerged exposed material is dependent upon substrate and oceanographic processes that are key drivers in site formation. An assumption in this model is that fishers avoid UCH sites for fear of damage or loss to fishing gear (Hickman et al., 2024). The variable weighting in this model is: 50% substrate, 20% velocity, 10% DO, 10% salinity and 10% temperature (Table 3).

Model 4: Preservation potential of UCH is equally dependent on all C- and N-transforms

Model 4 was developed to assess the contribution of each variable to site formation and preservation potential. Statistical inferences were drawn from the spatial correlation of the outputs, giving insights into the explanatory powers of each of the c- and n-transforms in site formation and site trajectories. All c- and n-transforms were weighted equally (Table 3).

1.4.5 Risk Assessment

Data mining of the environmental variables at each wreck site was conducted in QGIS v3.16 using the Point Sampling Tool (Plugin ID 223). In this scenario wrecks in the Irish Sea shipwreck databases are risk-classified according to Model 3. Individual wreck sites therefore inherit their risk classification from the model output. The results of the four models are presented below.

Model 1: Output for UCH buried completely beneath the seabed

Model 1 predicts highest preservation potential for buried material in the Western Irish Sea Mud Belt, the Firth of Clyde, and east of Islay (Fig. 14). In the area between Morecambe Bay and Solway Firth, and in the Celtic Sea to the south of St. George's Channel, high preservation potential is also noted. Lowest preservation potential is modelled for the seafloor northwest of Anglesey, parts of the Severn Estuary, the south coast of Ireland off Counties Waterford and Wexford, and to the west of the Llyn Peninsula.

Figure 14: Preservation potential modelled for buried material in the Irish Sea.

Model 2: Output for UCH semi-exposed at the seabed

Model 2, for UCH partially buried in the seafloor, is almost the reverse of Model 1, with areas of low archaeological potential predicted in many of the high-preservation potential areas of Model (Fig. 15). This can be explained by the fact that the fine-grained substrates which coincide with high preservation potential in Model 1 are the same areas targeted by commercial fishing in Model 2 (Fig. 13). Poorest preservation is predicted around the Isle of Arran, in the North Channel, the southern part of the Western Irish Sea Mud Belt, off Anglesey and the Llyn Peninsula, parts of the Severn Estuary and off the south coast of Ireland and into the Celtic Sea. High preservation potential is predicted in nearshore areas, away from commercial fishing grounds.

Figure 15: Preservation potential modelled for shallow-buried and semi-exposed material in the Irish Sea.

Model 3: Output for UCH fully exposed at the seabed

Model 3 predicts highest preservation potential for exposed UCH in the Western Irish Sea Mud Belt, the Firth of Clyde, east of Islay, the area between Morecambe Bay and Solway Firth, and in the Celtic Sea to the south of St. George’s Channel (Fig. 16). Lowest preservation potential is modelled for parts of the Severn Estuary, the south coast of Ireland off Counties Waterford and Wexford, and in the North Channel.

Figure 16: Preservation potential modelled for exposed material in the Irish Sea.

Model 4: Output for scenario where preservation potential is equally dependent on all C- and N-transforms

Model 4, where all C- and N-transforms are weighted equally, was developed to assess the contribution of each variable to site formation and preservation potential (Fig. 17). Moderate to strong correlations are noted between preservation and the n-transforms: depth, substrate, DO and temperature (Table 4). These relationships indicate that depth and substrate are two good proxies for preservation potential, and as both these parameters are included as fields in the UKHO wreck database, may be effective information for heritage managers. A weak negative correlation is noted between fishing intensity and preservation potential (Table 4), implying the impact of commercial fishing practices on UCH in the Irish Sea is potentially limited, at least at a regional scale.

Figure 17: General preservation model for UCH in the Irish Sea.

Table 4: Correlation statistics - Model 4 (n=2,052)

Variable	Correlation coefficient
Depth	+0.61
Substrate	+0.44
Velocity	+0.04
Salinity	+0.14
Dissolved oxygen	+0.57
Temperature	+0.68
Fishing intensity	-0.22

Risk assessment

Wrecks in the Irish Sea shipwreck databases are risk-classified according to Model 3. Individual wreck sites inherit their risk classification from the model output. The lowest risk sites are located around the Western Irish Sea Mud Belt, the Firth of Clyde, east of Islay, the area between Morecambe Bay and Solway Firth, and in the Celtic Sea to the south of St. George’s Channel (Fig. 18). The wreck sites at highest risk are in the Severn Estuary, off the coast of Wexford, to the northwest of Anglesey, the west of the Llyn Peninsula, in the North Channel and off the northeast of the Inishowen Peninsula.

Figure 18: Risk categories for individual wreck sites in the Irish Sea derived from Model 3.

1.4.6 Wreck trajectories

Introduction

Site formation and future wreck trajectories are a function of physical, chemical, biological and anthropogenic processes:

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = \frac{dP}{dt} + \frac{dC}{dt} + \frac{dB}{dt} + \frac{dA}{dt}$$

where D is disintegration, P represents physical processes, C represents chemical processes, B represents biological processes, and A represents anthropogenic intervention. In the Irish Sea, wreck site formation and future trajectories are therefore dependent on natural and anthropogenic forcing, governed by geological, oceanographic, chemical and biological processes, and human activities acting on a variety of spatial (from local to regional) and temporal scales.

Generalised regional-scale models

From the statistical analysis conducted on the Model 4 output, it is evident that site formation and future wreck trajectories in the Irish Sea are significantly influenced by water depth and substrate (Fig. 16; Table 4). Wrecks located in deep water and/or on fine-grained substrates are therefore predicted to survive longer. Conversely, wrecks in shallow water and/or on coarse substrates are projected to disintegrate more rapidly. These findings are backed up by other studies (e.g. Quinn, 2006; Keith and Evans, 2016), where substrate is identified as a key predictor in site preservation and evolution.

Figure 19: Conceptual model of wreck trajectories in the Irish Sea – a regional-scale model.

Site-specific models

Although a conceptual model for wreck trajectories in the Irish Sea has been developed at a regional scale (Fig. 19), this one-size-fits-all model can break down at a local scale, where linked hydro- and sediment-dynamics and/or high-impact short-lived events can cause significant changes to wreck systems over relatively short time periods. Examples are illustrated below using multibeam echosounder (MBES) data collected over four wreck sites in the Irish Sea.

The SS *W.M. Barkley* (lost 1918) site is a good example of where hydrodynamic forcing influences site formation at a sand-dominated location. Time-lapse MBES surveys conducted over four years allowed for the evaluation of long-term (2015–2019: Fig. 20a and 20b) and short-term (one week: Fig. 20c and 20d) change. Differences of -4.9 m and $+3.0$ m in bed elevation were observed over a four-year period (Fig. 20a), associated with sand wave migration, and the reorganisation of sediment within erosional and depositional signatures at the site. In terms of areal coverage, negative change (38.5% of the area) was more extensive than positive change (21.6% of the area), suggesting that the site is in a state of net erosion (Fig. 20b). The calculated mean bathymetric change (-0.17 m) also suggests net erosion. Interestingly, significant bathymetric changes are observed at the site even in the short-term (one week) (Fig. 20c).

Figure 20: Difference models for the SS W.M. Barkley site. (a) long-term model (2015-2019), (b) areal percentage histogram for the long-term model, (c) short-term model (one week, 2019), (d) areal percentage histogram for the short-term model (Majcher et al., 2022).

A wreck site that demonstrates evidence of rapid structural change in the Irish Sea is HMS Vanguard (lost 1875). The wreck site was originally surveyed using a MBES in 2015, and re-surveyed in 2019 (Majcher et al., 2022) using the same survey parameters. Five areas of structural change were captured in the resulting difference model (Fig. 21). The first region comprised a bending of the portside gunwale, displaced downwards by approximately 1.5 m (Fig. 21c, box 1). The second change is associated with one of the stern gunwales dropping 1 m towards the seabed (Fig. 21c, box 2). The third and fourth areas were related to the iron mainmast lowering by approximately 0.3 m. This change in the mainmast's position was associated with erosion of the seabed around its tip (Fig. 21c, boxes 3, 4). Finally, highly localized, but potentially high magnitude (-2.5m) changes were registered on the upper surface of the box battery (Fig. 21c, box 5), which may have been caused by plating falling into the hull (Majcher et al., 2022).

Figure 21: Structural change at the HMS Vanguard site. (a) point cloud of the 2015 survey, (b) point cloud of the 2019 survey, (c) difference model for the interval 2015-2019 (Majcher et al., 2022).

A final example from the Irish Sea (Fig. 22) shows time-lapse analysis of two multimodal sites (SS Polwell and FV St. Michan) which display minimal geomorphic change over a four-year period, in stark contrast to the SS W.M. Barkley site (Fig. 20). However, the FV St. Michan data does show anthropogenic interference, with trawl marks directly intersecting the shipwreck site (Fig. 22b and c). Similar trawling impacts patterns on wrecks are seen elsewhere in the Irish and North Seas (Gregory et al., 2024).

These case studies therefore clearly demonstrate examples of where the regional-scale conceptual model breaks down at a local scale. Therefore, instead of wreck trajectories being represented by smooth asymptotic curves (Fig. 19), at a site-specific scale wreck trajectories can sometimes be interrupted by external triggers or forcing events, ultimately leading to more complex trajectories (Fig. 23), and material loss at earlier stages.

Figure 22: Multiannual DEMs of difference with minor geomorphic changes for (a) SS Polwell, 2019–2015, (b) FV St. Michan, 2019–2015, and (c) inset map showing a multidirectional hillshade raster created using the 2019 DEM with FV St. Michan (Majcher et al., 2021).

Figure 23: Conceptual model of wreck trajectories in the Irish Sea – a site-specific model.

1.5 Case Study 2: New Discoveries Around the Isle of Man

Michael Roberts, Lara Band, Deanna Groom, Sarah Saunderson and Phoebe Wild

The second case study chosen to test and demonstrate the power of connected collections was our attempt to identify known and surveyed wrecks in the Irish Sea which were either unidentified, tentatively identified or possibly, incorrectly identified.

1.5.1 Study Area and Current State of Knowledge

The study area (Fig. 1) located in the northwestern Irish Sea selected for the wreck identification extends over an area of approximately 5000km² (almost 2000 square miles) located between the west coast of the Isle of Man (IOM) and the eastern coast of Northern Ireland (NI). The area is characterised by water depths typically ranging between 20m to 30m proximal to the shorelines in Northern Ireland and IOM, increasing up to 150m in the mid-channel region between coasts. The seabed comprises of a range of substates but typically dominated by fine grained muddy deposits in the deeper water regions with coarser materials being found closer to shore and towards the eastern, shallower regions, northwest of Liverpool Bay. Tidal currents are relatively moderate to weak compared to most other areas in the Irish Sea with little or no change in tidal height being experienced off the NI coast due to the configuration of water movement around the UK coastline.

As of September 2022, the UK Hydrographic Office (UKHO) database identified 122 sites in the offshore study area listed as being wrecks, obstructions or rough ground features (many unidentified features are routinely termed 'fishermen's fasteners' due to having been initially identified and reported through commercial trawling activity).

[Marine data sets - Access and download data from UKHO \(admiralty.co.uk\)](https://www.admiralty.co.uk/marine-data-sets)

Of the 122 sites listed, 61 have been assigned an identity, 50 are classified as being 'unknown' with no attempt in assigning a possible identity/attribution and 11 are listed as being obstructions, 'foul ground' or 'dead' (i.e. no wreck is present). Further research demonstrated that 7 of the 61 sites assigned identities have been independently confirmed as being correct via the collection of physical evidence (divers recovering the vessel's bell or obtaining other artifacts), whilst 2 others are of well-documented, relatively recent marine accidents. Of the remaining 52 sites with named 'attributions' the UKHO database classifies 8 as being 'probably' correct and 13 as being 'possibly' correct, with a further 31 having received no formal classification in terms of a confidence rating relating to their respective attributions.

1.5.2 Approach and Methodology

The UKHO database does not contain a comprehensive list of all vessels known to have been lost in any given area, therefore, to begin trying to identify the remains of vessels in a specified area, a detailed list of all potential vessels must be established. Perhaps unsurprisingly any such list of candidate vessels should/will exceed the total number of wrecks known to be present (assuming all wrecks in the defined area have been identified, which is often, far from the case, particularly with respect to smaller vessels of 20m or less). Consideration also needs to be given to the possibility that vessels may have been abruptly

lost in the study area whilst in transit, with no known record of it ever having been present within a particular geographical area.

An initial study as to the current state of knowledge with respect to wrecks in the selected area was undertaken to establish the 'current state of knowledge', i.e. what is 'known' to be correct, what is 'considered' to be correct and what is unknown. In addition to this, a list of candidate vessels, known or thought to have been lost in the study area was developed, this proved to be a significant challenge given that there is no established method for collating a definitive list of vessels lost in any specified geographical area. It rapidly became apparent that numerous archival resources and collections would need to be researched to ensure a meaningful and realistic proportion of candidate vessels could be identified. Given the scale of this task, available resource and limited timeframe, it was decided that efforts should therefore predominantly be focussed on larger vessels (>40m in length) made of iron/steel that were lost in the study area between the late Victorian era and mid-20th century. Simultaneously, work was undertaken to convert multibeam sonar data provided by Bangor University into grid model form for dimensional analysis and a series of georeferenced digital terrain models (DTM's) were generated.

The Maritime Chapter of the Archaeological Research Framework for Wales included the priority to target research at the substantial number of 'Unnamed Wrecks' around the coast for 2017-2021 and again in priorities set the 2021-2026 (Groom, ed. 2022). This reflects the substantial number of un-identified wrecks in Welsh waters (i.e. 500 or just under a 1/3 of the known and located wreck sites around the coast of Wales). The Isle of Man Historic Environment Record (IoMHER) and Historic Environment Record of Northern Ireland (HERoNI) have similar proportions of unidentified wreck sites. Many of these known wreck sites were last surveyed during the 1970's and 1980s, hence the present information about condition and extents is comparatively old. In addition, there are parts of the Irish Sea where the Civil Hydrography Programme recognises that there is only partial seafloor coverage (UKHO, 2024a). A paucity of existing data and resultant limited understanding as to what may be located to the west and south of the Isle of Man, which is one such site, was a key incentive for focussing Unpath'd Waters' Work Programme 3.2: Science and the Sea resources to this area.

Whilst diver reports and archaeological investigations have made and continue to make, a significant contribution to identifications being revised and updated, the opportunity to make use of the multibeam capabilities of the RV Prince Madog whilst on passage or undertaking a broad range of oceanographic measurements in the Irish Sea has been extraordinarily beneficial to National Monuments Records and Heritage Agencies. The majority of sunken vessels have not been seen since imaged by early sonar systems such as ASDIC or, indeed, since their time of loss and studies have suggested that the rates of corrosion for losses from the early part of the 20th century will soon begin to cause substantial structural collapse (Daley 2019). The surveys undertaken by Bangor University are therefore extremely timely in that they may provide a last opportunity to see these relics of our maritime past upstanding and largely intact. The lack of confirmed identity prohibits well-informed assessment of a site's significance in terms of implementing appropriate conservation measures and management, as well as preventing the full stories the vessel, its crew, and its historical context from being told.

Scotland has a National Marine Plan covering out to 200 nautical miles and a series of regional marine plans extending out to 12 nautical miles. The general principle for historic

environment is encapsulated in Gen 6: Development and use of the marine environment should be protected and, where appropriate, enhance heritage assets in a manner proportionate to their significance (Scottish Government 2015: 19). The Northern Ireland Marine Plan is still in the consultation phase, but promoting the preservation and enjoyment of marine related heritage assets forms one of the eight Plan Objectives ((DAERA 2018:47). The Isle of Man does not yet have a Marine Plan but instead a Manx Marine Environmental Assessment (MMEA) Report created under the Isle of Man Marine Plan Project. Chapter 5 deals Marine & Coastal Historic Environment (Isle of Man Government 2018). Two key objectives in the Welsh National Marine Plan are to protect and promote valuable seascapes and heritage assets (Objective 7) and provide a shared, accessible marine evidence base provide a mechanism for unique characteristics to be better understood (Objective 13) (Welsh Government 2019).

Research into any shipwreck site is often driven by the information that is necessary to assess cultural significance. Historic England uses historical, artistic, or archaeological importance (Historic England, 2017) as does the Isle of Man, with the criteria embodied in Manx legislation (Wreck and Salvage (ships and aircraft) Act 1979). Cadw expresses themes necessary to assessments as a wreck's physical remains and surviving fabric; pictorial and documentary records that help us to understand them; their capacity to illuminate aspects of the past and connect us to it; their aesthetic qualities; and the value they have to the people who relate to them (Cadw, 2011). Historic Scotland uses intrinsic, contextual, and associative characteristics (Historic Environment Scotland, 2019). For Northern Ireland the significance of heritage assets is assessed primarily through archaeological interest, historic interest and architectural interest, though other aspects of interest may be considered including symbolic interest or communal interest (Department for Communities, 2021).

To develop and test wreck identification methodologies, the area of the Irish Sea between Northern Ireland and the Isle of Man was chosen (Fig. 1). Within this area there are 188 records in the UK Hydrographic Office Wrecks and Obstructions dataset, 122 of which are 'live' and 91 are named wrecks. Removing vessels that sank less than 60 years ago, for ethical reasons, left 64 named wrecks. To these were added four more thought to have sunk within the study area, according to Lloyd's War Losses and Lloyd's Casualty Returns (Lloyd's 1990). Each researcher was then assigned a number of vessels to investigate. Where the date of loss was known, all the vessels were lost in the period 1857-1961, see Appendix 1 for a list of the vessels investigated. Given time and resource constraints of the project, priority vessels were chosen to investigate though initial research was undertaken for all vessels.

The assessment process began by drawing together archaeological, technological, and historical sources. The approach of developing a 'ship biography' was proposed by Wessex Archaeology in 2004 and forms a system of shipwreck assessment based on five factors which represent all phases of a ship's career covering: Build, Use, Loss, Survival, and Investigation or BULSI. This moved interpretation away from the idea of shipwrecks as 'time capsules' and examined them in the context in which they were built and used, the way they were lost, how they have survived and how they were investigated (Wessex Archaeology 2006). This approach, applied to vessels lost or presumed to be lost within Unpath'd Waters WP 3.2 study area, provided a means to systematically begin searching the UK's archive network to discover what information was available about each vessel that was available.

Two more themes were added – communal value and wider historical context - as can be seen in the BULSI figure below. In this case, communal value has been taken to include ways that people draw sensory and intellectual stimulation from a site (aesthetic value) along with the meanings that a site may have for people (Historic England 2008). This also fitted with the wider Unpath'd Waters aim of reaching new audiences, in particular non-coastal communities who are less likely to identify with maritime cultural heritage and cross-disciplinary natural science and cultural researchers. Many of the vessels identified for research were the casualties of the two World Wars, and hence likely to have a significant commemoration interest. Adding the wider context of maritime trade, combat in the Irish sea and the post-sinking lives of vessels to the BULSI framework, allowed our research to highlight narratives which explored a diverse range of concepts including the 'Theatre of War', global connections and colonialism, and biodiverse futures.

Figure 24: the BULSI themes approach to information gathering applied to the loss of SS Florrieston.

Two approaches to the identification process were taken. One approach was to start from the loss/survival phase of a vessel’s biography. Viewing the multibeam echosounder (MBES) imagery for a wreck allowed gathering of key information on overall dimensions, proportions, an impression of type of vessel from the shape of the hull and the stern and bow, the nature of the deck arrangements (if the vessel was upright), and any other features (e.g. funnels, superstructure) lying in close proximity to the principal wreck structure on the seabed.

These first impressions provide an initial indication of the type of vessels (e.g. merchant steamship, sailing vessel, U-boat, concrete lighter, or smaller vernacular craft such as the sloops, schooners, seagoing Mersey flats and Severn trow’s which undertook much of the coasting trade in the Irish sea in the 19th and early 20th century.

These indexing factors were then matched to existing wrecks data and documentary references to losses in the vicinity from the UKHO Wrecks and Obstructions data set (UKHO

2024b), and National Inventories for the Isle of Man, Northern Ireland, and Wales. GIS mapping containing these datasets provides the initial way of selecting identities for the wreck on the seabed.

Once these potential identities have been compiled, more detailed research was undertaken into their technical specifications, and the wreck on the seabed can be compared to any surviving photographs, paintings, ship models, and shipbuilders' plans and yard books.

Beginning with the vessel's build/use/loss phase provided an equally fruitful approach, particularly where a (supposed) identification already exists. Information gathered on a vessel's technical specification and appearance plus any details of damage suffered during loss was compared with the MBES data for the existing identification. In some cases, it was clear the wreck was misidentified so a search as described above would then be undertaken within the 12nm radius. Even if the wreck appeared to match, a search was still undertaken to check there were no other potential candidates in the vicinity.

For both approaches the process is iterative and may result in more than one possibility. Communication across the team was also an important factor: with a set of vessels to work on each, discounting an existing identity 'opened up' a new possibility for a wreck, as was the case for UKHO 5075, previously identified as SS Maja, but now thought likely to be HMS Stephen Furness (see Case Study c below).

1.5.3 Sources (scientific data, collections/archives, resources)

Online resources

A spreadsheet of resources used during our research forms an appendix to this report, many of which are available online. For each vessel a search across Canmore, Coflein, and the IoMHER and HERoNI viewers was the starting point to ascertain the extent of the national record. The freely downloadable Wrecks and Obstructions data set (UKHO 2024b) was also a valuable resource. The bibliographies associated with each record entry provide an indication of the resources accessed, which to review and what will need to be added after the research undertaken by Unpath'd Waters WP3.2 researchers.

Several online resources provided immediate access to useful technical information, including the secondary sources at Wrecksite.eu and Uboat.net. Three of the major UK centres of shipbuilding activity have online databases for ships built in their region (Clydeships, Sunderlandsips and the Aberdeen City Archive). These provide the ship's IMO number and Official numbers, which can be especially helpful in distinguishing records elsewhere, for ships with the same name; technical information about the ship and its builder and, sometimes, biographical details for the ship. The Lloyd's Register Foundation Heritage & Education Centre (LRFH&EC) provides scanned ship plans and survey documents as well as scanned copies of Lloyd's Register of Ships, Lloyd's Register of Yachts, Lloyd's of London Missing Vessels Books and Casualty Returns (aka Wreck returns). Crewlist (the Crew List Index Project) provides scans of the Mercantile Navy list as well as records of British seafarers. Crewlists can also be accessed via the 1915 Crew List project (Royal Museum Greenwich) and the National Archives portal Discovery.

Through online collections at the British Newspaper Archive, Welsh Newspapers (National Library of Wales) and Trove, the National Library of Australia's research portal, it was possible to find information about launches and ships trials, ship specifications, arrivals and departure from ports, and incidents in a ship's life such as going aground and collisions. For locally well-known and well-regarded ships and crews there may be contemporary newspapers articles and obituaries that provide information about an individual's background. Family history research platforms such as Ancestry and Find my Past (paywalled but free to access in libraries) provide opportunity to explore an individual's life in more detail. Biographical details may also be found in The Commonwealth War Graves Commission (CWGC) casualty database which holds records for 1.7million men and women of the Commonwealth forces and Merchant Navy, who died in the First and Second World Wars. Individuals can be searched for by name or, by entering a ship name as the 'Unit', most casualties from a particular vessel can be found. Records always indicate the nationality of the seafarer but details on familial relationships are largely absent, for example, for the Indian Merchant Service (First World War) and Indian Merchant Navy (Second World War). Some records in their wider archive are also available online.

The wealth of information scattered across the internet cannot be underestimated, whether relating to specific vessels or associated individuals. These range from the webpages of the Royal Fleet Auxiliary Historical Association to enthusiast websites such as customscowes.co.uk or Rolls of Honour such as masonicgreatwarproject.org.uk. Mersea Museum website (<https://www.merseamuseum.org.uk>) has images of some of the crew that were lost with RFA Industry and refers to a book published by the museum which has further details of the lives of the men who were lost in the incident (Bullen 2000). Also, 'The Life-Boat', The Journal of the Royal National Life-boat Institution (<https://lifeboatmagazinearchive.rnli.org/>) has been digitised, it contains reports of incidents and rescues between the years 1852-2019 can be searched here and was a resource was used for the StoryMap of MV Tuskar (Saunderson, 2024a). Often these were useful for only one or two vessels in the study area but brought information not found elsewhere. Altogether they illustrate the breadth of sources and information available online.

Physical archives

As well as allowing searches across 2500 other archive collections through its Discovery portal, the National Archives at Kew provides a rich source of information on the context in which the ships were operating, plus individual vessel biographies and losses. The series BT 165 (Board of Trade - Registry of Shipping and Seamen: Ships' Official Logs), for example, covers the period 1902-1919, and contains crewlists (though see the case study for SS Peshawur, below), details of voyages, and day to day management including rules, regulations and punishments for transgressions and notes on crew sickness. The series ADM 137/3965 - ADM 137/4019 (Enemy Submarines: particulars of attacks on merchant vessels in home waters) and ADM 137/1362, ADM 137/1514 - ADM 137/1517 (Irish Sea: German Submarines) provided access to eye-witness accounts to submarine attacks during World War I relevant to many of our case studies. The series BT 365 Board of Trade and successors: War Risks Insurance Records allows detailed interrogation of what might otherwise only appear as passing references 'general cargo', see the StoryMap for SS Kafue (Saunderson, 2024b). The National Archives also includes the Port of London Shipping Registers for records of ownership and financing. The archives also hold transcripts of other port registers and, on occasion, the stained and worn Ship Registration document from the ship's onboard papers returned after loss.

Figure 25: Naval vessels, such as Oropesa/HMS Champagne, may have surviving Ship's logs. One can see exactly what patrolling entailed on the frontline of the Northern Blockade of Germany during 1915-1915. (ADM 53/53775 OROPESA | The National Archives).

Significant maritime archive holdings can be found at many of the major shipbuilding centres and major port cities (e.g. Tyne and Wear Archives and Newcastle Discovery; The Scottish Maritime Museum, Irvine; the Scottish Business Records Centre, Glasgow University; Merseyside Maritime Museum and Archives Centre and Liverpool City Council Archives Centre). These are often linked to the ship builder and may include directors' minutes from board meetings, Yard Books which detail the technical specification for the vessel, and any ships plans not held in the national collections. Two other important types of record providing technical information, Port Shipping Registers and Port Fishing Boat Registers, are now also held within regional archive services. Port Registers can be especially informative about smaller vessels, which formed the core of the coasting trade and fishing industry, and which were not insured at Lloyd's.

Regional archives are free to access, but most will require a visit in person to determine whether documents of relevance have survived. These centres also have local history libraries where published works can be accessed to provide invaluable context. They may also provide access to sites behind paywalls such as the British Newspaper Archive and genealogy websites. Other physical archives include the Royal National Lifeboat Institution (RNLI) archive at its headquarters at Poole, where services rendered to wrecked vessels has been researched and collated by station by the Lifeboat Enthusiasts Society. The original records for services rendered and payments to the crews are often held in regional archives.

Visual material essential for seabed wreck identification

Whilst an extensive range of ship plans are available via the LRFH&EC website, as mentioned above the availability of ship plans to aid research is a challenge – access to large collections, such as the those at Royal Museums Greenwich or the Harland and Wolf archive at the Ulster Transport Museum, remains problematic for researchers because of lack of accessible catalogues.

A similar issue exists for ship models. Some museums have published their catalogues and some images online such as Glasgow Museums and the Science Museum Group. The Imperial War Museum also has photographs of each vessel in its extensive collection of

Dazzle painted models. However, collections of regional and local maritime museums, and businesses such as shipping and insurance companies, have models which cannot be found through online searches.

Online access to photographic collections remains partial. Some are available online such as Cumbria Archives' Sankey Collection, the Allen Collection, Dundee City Archives or the Australian National Maritime Museum. Other collections cannot be searched online and require an email request to the collections team, such as for the National Museum of Wales. This may reflect the fragility of some image collections (e.g. glass plate negatives) and lack of internal resources. There may also be problems associated assigning identities to the vessel shown, dates images were taken, and copyright ownership, which all lead to only small parts of collections being made available online. At present time, one of the largest photographic collections – the World Ship Society – does not provide digital prints or sell photographs from its collections.

Another important resource for vessel images are contemporary postcards some of which may have been published by shipping lines as part of publicity activities. Surviving postcard publishers such as Francis Frith and Judges are digitising their historic collections and making the images available. Other picture postcard publishers work can be found on auctions sites such as eBay. Contemporary newspapers may of course also have images of vessels, or even crew members. Other illustrative sources include Divernet, which provides access to 180 descriptions and illustrations of wrecks underwater. However, the sites providing the focus for WP3.2 research lie much deeper than the recommended limit of 30m depth for sports diving on air, and hence few wrecks in the WP3.2 study area can be found on this website.

Wrecks Data and Bangor University Multibeam Echosounder Data

The UKHO Wrecks and Obstructions data set (UKHO, 2024b) contains data from a rich variety of sources including surveys by Royal Navy Vessels and survey contractors from the Civil Hydrographic Programme; reports of sinking in Notices to Mariners; reports of temporary buoyage placed by Trinity House and harbour authorities whilst the vessel has been judged a navigational hazard; reports of dismantling and wreck clearance; and reports of salvage under Government contract by companies such as Rizdon Beazley. Data for smaller, low height profile obstruction may be possibly much older wreck sites. These are often reported as the fishermen's fastenings or foul grounds for anchoring.

In some instances, queries raised by the Wrecks Section own staff and the obvious mismatch between the sonar contact dimensions and the ship purported to be will have prompted research to resolve the identification when the Wrecks data was brought into the NMRs/HER during monument record creation. For example, a likely identity may have been found within the documentary references to losses recorded in the NMRs/HER. The inclusion of documentary records for losses in standard maritime record recreation is specifically for this purpose and to provide an indication of the archaeological potential of any area of seabed.

Where the identity of the loss has not been positively confirmed, normal practice is to create a 'Unnamed wreck' record for the archaeological site, and a separate documentary loss record for the vessel's name, containing the event and historical context for the loss.

Relationship records are created in the background which allow the recording of 'possible identify.' These potential relationships are often also flagged in the site description texts. The information contained in the Wrecks and Obstructions data set includes the dimension of the sonar contact, its long-axis orientation, whether the wreck is upright and the height of

the wreck above the seabed in relation to the safe navigational clearance. Dimensional information is especially important in terms of initially identifying wrecks on the seabed.

The multibeam acquisition software, plus free viewers such as Fledermaus 8.6.1 have tools which allow features to be measured and the site's height above the seabed to be gauged. The way a ship is lying on the seabed will determine which measurements are possible, for example if a wreck is lying on its side, the height above the seabed will give an indication of the breadth of the vessel while measurements for overall length may have to be estimated from two or more parts of the vessel lying a distance apart. A combination of size and overall shape of the wreck will provide an indication of the type of vessel. In 1944, US military intelligence published an identification guide for vessels, which remains useful today to record impressions of the wreck such as type of bow, stern, number of islands or built-up bulwarks, and configuration of superstructures and masts (US Navy 1944)

Figure 26: the multibeam echosounder survey of site UKHO 5381 reveals that it has similar dimensions and features to the World War II ferro-concrete barges abandoned at Purton, River Severn (source: National Register of Historic Vessels, FCB 67 FCB67 | National Historic Ships)

1.5.4 Results and Vessel Case Studies

The results of information identified for each vessel researched was collated into MS Word documents containing key information about the vessel, its unique identification numbers plus links to sources and extracts of key information. A total of 68 vessels were researched in total (appendix 1). The sources identified were collated into an MS Excel spreadsheet along with links and access information. The number of online resources identified numbered 113 and are shown in (appendix 2). These word documents and the MS Excel spreadsheets will be provided to the IoMHER, RCAHMMW, and HERoNI to enable further enhancement of their records.

As of August 2024, of the 113 unconfirmed wreck sites within the study area:

- 25 (22%) previously unknown or unconfirmed have been identified, re-named or confirmed as a direct consequence of Unpath'd Waters research.
- 49 (43%) of surveyed sites identified or confirmed as being geological features

- 5 (4%) of surveyed sites identified as being debris or unidentifiable
- 34 (30%) of surveyed wreck sites remain unknown or unconfirmed and require further investigation

The following case studies (a-i) were chosen from fifteen wrecks specifically researched for Unpath'd Waters WP3.2. They have been chosen to illustrate methodology, resources and archives encountered during the research undertaken as well as highlighting the opportunities and challenges. A non-exhaustive list of resources consulted during the research is included with each case study; this includes material consulted during the writing of the case studies for this report. Some of the case studies were additionally utilised to create publicly accessible ArcGIS based StoryMaps, published on the project webpage (unpathdwaters.org.uk/science-and-the-sea). These were created to meet our work package's aim of discovering and disseminating new/novel vessel and wreck-based narratives thereby increasing awareness of and engagement with UK maritime cultural heritage with a view to attracting a broader audience.

a) SS Maja: an example on approaching wreck identification (Lara Band)

Overview

SS Maja was built in 1883 in Sunderland by SP Austin & Son for Johnson Brothers & Co. Originally named Western Star (Official no. 86975), the 1452-ton iron screw steamer was sold in 1885 following the bankruptcy of Edward Smith Johnson (BNA, HHT&N, Wear Built Ships). The steamer changed hands several times, was renamed Neva in 1891 under C.M. Norwood & Co, London and reregistered with Official no. 4489 in 1907 following acquisition in 1905 by Rederi Ab Karnan, Helsingborg. In 1917 Neva was acquired by Rederi Ab Tertia, Gothenburg, under Director Ivar Lignell, likely the famed yacht racer and tennis player, and renamed Maja (Gothenburg University Library, LRFH&EC, Project Runeberg, Wear Built Ships). On 11 October 1918 Maja, chartered by the Italian Government and en-route from Glasgow to either Rochefort or Blaye, France, was torpedoed and sunk by UB 126. Nine crew members died (Adrian Corkill pers. comm, TNA, U-boat.net, Wear Built Ships, Wrecksite).

The UKHO Wrecks and Obstructions data set lists two positions for Maja: UKHO 5056 is marked as "dead" however and points to UKHO 5075. This is mirrored in Canmore and HERoNI. HERoNI record SWR105 also refers to the wreck as 'Maga or Maja'.

Associated UKHO and Historic environment record numbers				
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore	IoMHER	Coflein
5075	SWR105	323098	-	-
5056 (dead, see 5075)	SWR106	323080	-	-

Archival Sources

- British Newspaper Archive: inc. North Star (1884) Bankruptcy of a West Hartlepool Ship Owner, 3 December, p4 <https://britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/viewer>
- Gothenburg University Library: Hvar 8 Dag (1919) Göteborgs Kungliga Segelsällskaps [...] regatta [...], p691-692 https://gupea.ub.gu.se/bitstream/handle/2077/64812/gupea_2077_64812_1.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

- TNA (The National Archives): ADM 137/1517 Irish Sea: German Submarines, July-Nov 1918
- LRH&EC: Lloyd's Register of Shipping (1885, 1907, 1915) and Neva (Ship Plans and Survey Reports) <https://hec.lrfoundation.org.uk/archive-library>
- Project Runeberg: Nordiska Familjeboken (1943) Lignell, Ivar A., pp71-72. Stockholm: Förlagsaktiebolaget A. Solman & Co. <https://runeberg.org/sportlex/5/0054.html>

Database Sources

- Canmore: Records 323080, 323098
- HERoNI: Records SWR105, SWR106
- U-boat.net: Maja https://U-boat.net/wwi/ships_hit/3837.htm
- UKHO: Wrecks and Obstructions data set, 2024
- Wear Built Ships: Western Star.
http://www.sunderlandships.com/view.php?year_built=&builder=&ref=100580&vesel=WESTERN+STAR
- Wrecksite: SS Maja [+1918] <https://www.wrecksite.eu/wreck.aspx?64857>

Additional sources

- Adrian Corkill (pers comm, various dates)
- Band, L. 2024. SS Maja: Combining archive research and seabed surveys to identify wrecks (Unpath'd Waters Science and the Sea StoryMap, 12 June 2024) <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/82d22c489ba149e596c94ff1afa8f630>
- HHT&N (Hartlepool History Then and Now): Western Star - a general history. <http://hhtandn.org/notes/1510/western-star-a-general-history>
- Horsburgh, K.J., Hill, A.E., Brown, J., (1998). A Summer Jet in the St George's Channel of the Irish Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 47(3), 285-294. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ecss.1998.0354/bl/0003631/18841203/004/0004>
- Wild, P. (2024) HMS Stephen Furness: Missing in action <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/bf1ccaff12ad4fab871714514a449a4f>

Method and results

Initial sources and archives approached included Wrecksite, U-boat.net and regional shipbuilding database Wear Built Ships. The details of the shipbuilding yard, construction date, dimensions, and previous names from these then helped identify plans and entries in Lloyd's Registers of Shipping, freely available online (LRFH&EC). Accounts of the sinking, based on sworn interviews with the Swedish Master Soot-Tissel and Norwegian Boatswain Olaf Olsen (TNA ADM 137/1517) describe how the ship broke in two and sank immediately following a torpedo strike on the boiler room.

MBES data for UKHO 5075, visualised in Fledermaus Viewer 8.6.1, showed that this wreck was intact. It was also too long and incorrectly proportioned compared to the shipbuilders' plan and Lloyd's Registers (LRFH&EC). It was clear therefore that UKHO 5075 could not be Maja.

In ADM 137/1517, there are two positions for Maja's sinking: "54.12.30.N, 5.36.00.W" (Soot-Tissel, 416) aligns with UKHO 5056; the Boatswain's "15 miles east of Ardglass [...] position only approximate" (Olsen, p425) matches UKHO 5075 in distance if not precise direction. To search for Maja, the UKHO Wrecks and Obstructions data set was loaded into QGIS 3.30.0. As previous Unpath'd Waters research indicates wrecks are typically within 12 nautical miles (NM) of their reported position an elliptical search zone was created encompassing UKHO 5075 and UKHO 5056. The ellipse was extended slightly southward since the Boatswain's raft was found 12 miles southeast of Ardglass. The east-west dimension was narrowed based on the Captain's last known direction and the influence of a southward current on the Irish Sea's western side (Horsburgh et al., 1998): this was an assumption made to reduce the initial search area; for discussion of specific drift calculation, see the Stephen Furness Case Study in this report.

Dead records, foul ground and wrecks right on the coast edge were discarded from the UKHO data. This left 28 candidates. The MBES data was visualised in Fledermaus Viewer 8.6.1 and CloudCompare v2.13 then compared with archival information. Only one candidate matched Maja's size, proportions, construction details, and damage: UKHO 5064. Halfway between UKHO 5075 and UKHO 5056, this position was also only 1NM southwest of the position UB 126 recorded for the attack in the KTB (*Kriegstagebuch*; Michael Lowrey (pers. Comm., 1 May 2024).

Identifying UKHO 5064 as Maja facilitated re-appraisal of the identity of UKHO 5075. After further research UKHO 5075 was identified as HMS Stephen Furness, whose sinking resulted in the loss of 101 lives but whose position had never been ascertained: see the Case Study in this report and the associated Unpath'd Waters StoryMap (Wild 2024).

Discussion

Research for Maja successfully integrated scientific data and archive sources to identify a previously unknown wreck, leaving the previously misidentified wreck open for reinterpretation. As a StoryMap (Band 2024) it presented this methodology to the public highlighting, at least in part, some of the methods they could use to research wrecks and vessels.

Archive research linked the UKHO numbers with the conflicting eyewitness accounts in, which allowed reappraisal of data discrepancies and aided identification. 'Maja or Maga' (HERoNI SWR105) can also be traced back to ADM 137/151: only the interviewers of Boatswain Olaf Olsen name the vessel Maga> this suggests the Boatswain may have been from southern Norway, where accents are more guttural. The Master's claim they were zigzagging and the Boatswain's claim they weren't, among other discrepancies in their accounts, hint at tension between the two men. Neither of these observations, or the bankruptcy story, were explored further but they give a glimpse into the lives and perspectives of those they document, humanising the archives and offering potential narratives to explore.

b) SS Peshawur: beyond wreck identification: colonial legacies (Lara Band)

Overview

SS Peshawur (IMO 121223) was a 7634-ton refrigerated cargo ship built in 1905 by Barclay, Curle & Co. Ltd., Glasgow, for The Peninsular and Orient Navigation Company. A sister ship to SS Poona, Peshawur had limited passenger accommodation and was designed for Far East and Australian service. Requisitioned by the Admiralty in 1914 as HM Squadron Supply Ship No. 1, Peshawur then served with H.M. Transport from May 1915. On 9 October 1917, while en route from Sydney, Nova Scotia to France with general goods, Peshawur was torpedoed by U 96 and sank off Ballyquintin Point, Co Down, Northern Ireland. (BNA, Wrecksite, RFAHA, RMG).

Either 11 (Wrecksite) or 13 (P&O) of the 125 onboard lost their lives. Research explored gaps in archival records and also uncovered a handwritten list of the belongings of Lascar seafarer, Shafkhan Caderbux Khan, who took his own life in 1910 (TNA). This informed a StoryMap (Band, 2024) examining archives, colonialism and institutional racism.

Associated UKHO and historic environment record numbers				
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore	IoMHER	Coflein
5068	SWR071	323091	-	-
5066 (dead, see 5068)	-	323089	-	-

Archival Sources

- LRFH&EC: Lloyd’s Register of Shipping <https://hec.lrfoundation.org.uk/archive-library>
- RMG: Bridges, poop/forecastle, upper & main decks plan of Peshawur (1905). National Maritime Museum, Greenwich, Barclay Curle Collection, Box BCAB0299
- TNA (The National Archives): TNA ADM137/1362 *Irish Sea: German Submarines, 1917*; ADM137/1365 *North West Approach: German Submarines, 16 August-31 December 1917*; ADM137/4002 *Enemy submarines: particulars of attacks on merchant vessels in home waters*; BT 165/465 *Extracted logs* [various ships, 1910]
- P&O Heritage: Peshawur fact sheet and photograph www.poheritage.com, <https://prints.poheritage.com/products/pod457275>
- CWGC: CWGC/1/1/9/E/12 (WG 998/2 PT.1), <https://archive.cwgc.org/>

Database Sources

- Canmore: Records 323091, 323089
- CWGC: <https://www.cwgc.org/find-records/find-war-dead>
- HERoNI: Record SWR071
- Scottish Built Ships: <https://www.clydeships.co.uk>
- UKHO Wrecks and Obstructions data set, 2024
- U-boat.net: https://U-boat.net/wwi/ships_hit/4759.html
- Wrecksite.eu: <https://www.wrecksite.eu/wreck.aspx?10523>

Other sources

- Band, L. 2020. SS Peshawur: A roll of green ribbon (Unpath'd Waters Science and the Sea StoryMap 28 June 2024)
<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/0db8a87ac88e40498684461f02617345>
- Adrian Corkill (pers. Comm., various dates)
- CWGC. 2021. Report of the Special Committee to Review Historical Inequalities in Commemoration <https://www.cwgc.org/non-commemoration>
- Derrida, J., 1995, Archive Fever: A Freudian Impression, in *Diacritics* 1996, 25:2, pp 9-63.
https://monoskop.org/images/9/99/Derrida_Jacques_1995_Archive_Fever_A_Freudian_Impression.pdf
- George, Rose. 2013. *Deep Sea Foreign Going*. London: Granta
- Khalili, Leila. 2024. *The Corporeal life of seafaring*. Np.: MACK
- Michael Lowrey (U-boat logs, pers. comm)
- Mbembe, A., 2002, The Power of the Archive and its Limits. In *Refiguring the Archive*, ed. by Hamilton, C., Harris, V., Taylor, J., Reid, G., Pickover, M., Saleh, R. Dordrecht: Springer Science+Business Media, pp19-26. <https://book.cc/book/2146927/6d87a7?id=2146927&secret=6d87a7>
- Naval-history.net, various pages
- Ahuja, R. 2012. Capital at Sea, Shaitan Below Decks? A Note on Global Narratives, Narrow Spaces, and the Limits of Experience . *History of the Present*, 2(1)
<https://doi.org/10.5406/historypresent.2.1.0078>
- RFAHA (Royal Fleet Auxiliary Historical Association): <https://historicalrfa.uk/>
- Siblon, J, 2016, Negotiating Hierarchy and Memory: African and Caribbean Troops form Former British Colonies in London's Imperial Spaces, *The London Journal*, 41:3, 299-312, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03058034.2016.1213548>
- Tower Hill Memorial (via www.benjidog.co.uk)

Method and results

Initial sources for Peshawur such as HERONI, Canmore, wrecksite.eu, U-boat.net, naval-history.net, the regional shipbuilding database (clydeships.co.uk) and Lloyd's Registers online (LRFH&EC) provided details such as the wrecks location, construction details, dimensions, and history. P&O Heritage have a factsheet and a photograph online, while the RFAHA website provided information on Peshawur's war service, though mistakenly uses an image of the SS Peshawur built for P&O in 1919. Extensive plans for Peshawur and Poona are held by Royal Museums Greenwich in the Barclay Curle Collection.

The sinking of SS Peshawur is detailed in TNA ADM137/1362, ADM137/1365, and ADM137/4002: a torpedo struck the port side near the engine room followed by a second on the starboard side half an hour later. Peshawur listed 20% then sank around 2 hours later. MBES data for UKHO 5068, visualized in Fledermaus Viewer 8.6.1, shows an intact wreck on its side. This matched archive details for dimensions and damage. With no other likely candidates within a 12NM radius, UKHO 5068 seems likely to be the correct identification for Peshawur. There is also a very detailed account of the sinking in U-96's KTB.

Initial sources disagreed on the number of crew lost. The CWGC casualty database, from which the wrecksite information is taken, lists 11 crew members, with two commemorated

at Tower Hill and 9 on the 'Bombay 1914-1918 Memorial, Mumbai'. This division sparked initial interest in what became the main 'story' for Peshawur. At Tower Hill, from the Mercantile Marine, are Wallace George Caws, Third Engineer and William James Andrews, Winchman. For both the database gives their age and biographical details, of parents, partner, place of residence and birth. Commemorated at Mumbai, from the 'Indian Merchant Service', are Abdullah Wahib, Trimmer; Akbar Falah Khan, Fireman; Kammu Maubarak, Trimmer; Maula Dad Khushi Muhammad, Fireman; Miyan Gulab Ali, Fireman; Shukrullah Jan Muhammad, Storekeeper; Nizamdin Umar, Fireman; Rahmat Rahim Bakhsh, Fireman and Sakhya Karamdin, Trimmer. There are no further biographical details, and their names are only in the 'Surname' column of the CWGC database, so it unclear whether they are recorded family name or forename first.

Eye-witness accounts held help to explain the discrepancy in the number of dead. Two interviews with Peshawur's Master (TNA ADM 137/1365, ADM 137/1362) report 13 killed: the winchman, third engineer, and 11 'British Indian Natives'. The Mercantile Marine Awards Committee's deposition (in TNA ADM 137/1365) also states there were 13 casualties. An officer from HM Yacht Albion III (in ADM 137/1365) which assisted Peshawur, reports the winchman, 3rd engineer, and 9 'lascars' killed, with 2 'lascars' needing immediate medical attention.

Discussion

The aim to identify the wreck of Peshawur (UKHO 5068) was achieved, with the caveat that 100% certainty is impossible. A parallel aim was to confirm the number of dead. Conflicting reports in ADM 137/1365 and ADM 137/1362 are the likely cause of discrepancies in sources today though the CWGC database suggests that the two injured crew members survived.

To definitively confirm the number of dead does not feel straightforward however: research into the life history of Peshawur exposed a broader pattern of omission and erasure of seafarers from the Global South. Crewlists in Peshawur's logbooks (TNA BT 165/465, and others in the same series), These logbooks, which were standard issue at the time, name seafarers signed on under 'European articles'. For 'Lascars and Asiatic Seamen' only a total number is given: their names are only recorded in discipline, injury or death, as for Shafkhan Caderbux Khan.

The colonial hierarchy that deemed these lives less important, or valuable, is mirrored in the Imperial War Graves Commission's decision to exclude "native" seafarers from the "British and foreign European" memorial at Tower Hill (Siblon, 2016; CWGC/1/1/9/E/12 (WG 998/2 PT.1)). References to difficulties in verification of names, the inability to distinguish Indians and East Africans and, for expediency, letting West African seafarers names 'slip into' the eventual memorial at Mumbai shows how entrenched this attitude was (ibid.).

While records for Lascar seafarers may be in the National Archives of India (see Ahuja 2012), gaps in British archives for Peshawur highlight colonial and racial biases in historical documentation. The CWGC has an ongoing project to review inequalities in commemoration though the initial report does not mention the Merchant Navy (CWGC 2021). The lack of detailed records for non-European seafarers distorts the British Empire's maritime history, downplaying the equal contributions of Lascars and other seafarers. The Tower Hill Memorial, a physical and very public manifestation of an archive, reflects and perpetuates the whitewashing of the Merchant Navy's war effort. Exposure of archival silence through

the lens of Peshawur (Band 2024) aimed to present a historical narrative that recognised the contribution of all who shaped our maritime world.

In line with Unpath'd Waters' goal to reach non-coastal communities and cross-disciplinary researchers, Peshawur's narrative also shone a light on the labour and lives of essential yet invisible global supply chain workers. Recognizing that "the UK's relationship with the sea impacts everyone [...]. Everyone eats food and wears clothes that have had a long journey across the sea" (<https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/about/>), we aimed to highlight the harsh reality that seafarers from the Global South continue to face more exploitative working conditions today than those from the Global North (Khalili, 2024; Rose, 2013). Archives define the past and therefore have power to create the future (Derrida 1995, Mbembe 2002:26). Researchers must always question how archives perpetuate the circumstances that create them and, in our reuse of archives, we must take care not to amplify the same bias.

c) HMS Stephen Furness: missing in action (Phoebe Wild)

Overview

HMS Stephen Furness was built in 190 by Irvine's Shipbuilding & Drydock Co. Ltd., West Hartlepool. It was built as a 1712 ton passenger vessel, but by 1917, was being operated as an armed boarding cruiser by the Royal Navy. On 13th December 1917, Stephen Furness was travelling from Lerwick to Liverpool but was torpedoed and sunk by UB-64, approximately 15 miles from Contrary Head, Isle of Man. The vessel sank in just three minutes, approximately 100 crew were lost. The UKHO does not record a location for Stephen Furness, although the admiralty records the sinking position as 54° 15'N , 5°07'W. A review of the multibeam data for this area shows that there are no suitable candidates for Stephen Furness in the immediate vicinity of this position. Further investigation was required to find the wreck site. Additionally, several graves of sailors from Stephen Furness are located on the north Welsh coast after having been washed ashore. This is over 70 miles from the Admiralty sinking location, as such, an investigation into the ocean dynamics that brought the sailors to Wales was necessary.

Current identification numbers				
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore	IoMHER	Coflein
-	-	-	1724	-

Archival Sources

- The National Archives: <https://discovery.nationalarchives.gov.uk/>
- Commonwealth War Graves: <https://www.cwgc.org/>
- National Archives and Records Administration (various dates), 1984. Microfilmed Records of the German Navy. T1022. Washington DC: NARA
- Met Office Digital Library and Archive: <https://digital.nmla.metoffice.gov.uk/>

Database Sources

- IOMHER: 1794
- UKHO: 5075, Wrecks and Obstructions data set, 2024

- Wrecksite: HMAV Stephen Furness (+1917)
<https://www.wrecksite.eu/wreck.aspx?141286>

Other Sources

- Band, L (2024) SS Maja: Combining archive research and seabed surveys to identify wrecks. <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/82d22c489ba149e596c94ff1afa8f630>

Method and results

The search for Stephen Furness began with information gathered from the National Archives, which included the court martial papers following the loss of Stephen Furness. This included a description of the sinking by Lieutenant PS Simmonds, one of the few survivors of the attack. His description stated the ship's position when torpedoed was Lat. 54° 15' N. Long. 5° 7' W" and that the ship sank in 3 minutes. However, review of multibeam data at this location indicated that this position was likely incorrect, as there are no seabed remains at this site, nor in the immediate vicinity, that would match the dimensions of Stephen Furness. Additionally, alternative sources suggest that the position provided by PS Simmonds was actually the position that survivors were picked up by the trawler *Elite*, over two hours after the sinking. This further reinforced that the Stephen Furness sank elsewhere- nearby, but not at 54° 15' N, 5° 07' W.

As such, alternative sources were sought for the sinking event. The sinking of the Stephen Furness from the crew's perspective was well recorded by PS Simmonds, and so the only other perspective that might shed some light on the sinking location would be that of UB-64. During the war, U-boat commanders often used a war diary or *Kriegstagebuch* (KTB) to describe the routes taken by their submarines, note any ships sighted, and detail any attacks carried out. The KTB entry for UB 64 on 13th December 1917 was reviewed (*Kriegstagebuch*; Michael Lowrey (pers. Comm., 1 May 2024). Translation of these documents described sighting a 'large, green painted auxiliary cruiser', and the subsequent torpedoing and sinking of the vessel. It also noted that the ship sank in three minutes. The positions recorded in the KTB were mapped and reviewed against multibeam data for the area. Less than 3 kilometres northeast of the position of UB64 when it torpedoed Stephen Furness, is a wreck (UKHO 5075). This vessel was previously identified as *Maja* (sunk in 1918); however, this identity was disproved by other research as part of the *Unpath'd Waters* project; see the Case Study in this report and the associated StoryMap (Band 2024). The dimensions of UKHO 5075 match those of the Stephen Furness. As such, there is reasonable evidence to conclude that UKHO 5075 is the Stephen Furness. This site represents the final resting place of the majority of the crew of this vessel.

Whilst most of the crew of Stephen Furness are commemorated at naval memorials in Portsmouth, Plymouth, Chatham, Ramsgate, and even Halifax in Canada, a handful of sailors are commemorated at different sites on the Isle of Man and north Welsh coast. Five sailors washed up on the Isle of Man (40 miles east of the sinking location) and are buried at Douglas Cemetery. Four sailors were washed up on beaches on the north Welsh coast- up to 100 miles southeast of the sinking position. The bodies of Walter Talmey, Alastair George, and Joseph Hall, and a further unknown sailor were washed up around a month after the Stephen Furness sank.

The fact that the bodies were washed up so far from the sinking position was a source of intrigue, and so it was decided to investigate the hydrographic and aeolian factors that caused this. Numerical modelling by colleagues in the School of Ocean Sciences at Bangor University was undertaken to investigate this in more detail (see 'Novel Applications' chapter). The key data source was the Met Office archives from which wind data could be extracted. Data from the 42 days following the 13th December 1917 was used to inform particle tracking modelling. The parameters for the model were as follows:

- 2000 particles released every hour for the first 24 hours from 13th December 1917 within 1km of UKHO 5075.
- Particles influenced by historic tidal and wind data (wind drift = 2% of wind speed)

The model was run, and the particles took the following route:

- For the first few hours, the particles remain in the vicinity of the wreck, before becoming more dispersed.
- They begin drifting east towards the west coast of the Isle of Man from the 15th December.
- They hit the west coast of the Isle of Man from the 16th December, wrapping round the south and lower east coast across the later hours of the 16th to the 18th of December.
- From the latter half of the 18th of December, they begin drifting southwest into the open channel between Ireland and North Wales.
- From the 1st January, the particles form a linear group and hit the Irish coast between the Skerries and Wicklow.
- They begin drifting east from the 6th January towards Wales.
- The first particles hit the tip of the Llŷn Peninsula on the 9th and 10th January before travelling northeast.
- They hit Anglesey from the 12th January before becoming stranded around the west coast of Anglesey, Llŷn Peninsula, and west coast of Wales to the south of the Llŷn Peninsula.

The particle tracking accurately demonstrates the route of the bodies that washed up on the Isle of Man and north Wales, and lines up with the dates that the bodies were discovered. The particle tracking results further reinforce that UKHO 5075 is the wreck of Stephen Furness.

Discussion

The identification of the wreck of Stephen Furness was achieved through integrating archival data to determine a position to compare with modern multibeam data. The additional proofing through hydrographical modelling added an interesting avenue for research and investigation, highlighting the breadth and depth of historical archives relevant to shipwreck research. The position for Stephen Furness' wreck was well described in the German KTB. In similar cases where no position is known for lost ships sunk by U-boats, it is likely that review of KTB entries would assist in locating their wreck sites.

d) SS Rostrevor: unexpected women in shipping (Phoebe Wild)

Overview

SS Rostrevor was built in 1899 in Paisley by John Fullerton & Company for the Newry & Killkeel Steamship Company owned by Joseph Fisher & Sons (Official no. 108644). Rostrevor was a 273-ton steamer, of approximately 43 metres in length. On 12th April 1917, the steamer was travelling between Newry and Manchester, when the cargo of granite setts it was transporting shifted, causing the vessel to founder and then sink approximately 25 miles northwest of the Skerries (Anglesey). The crew of nine were able to escape into lifeboats and were later picked up by the Glaswegian steamer Jargoan en route from Waterford to North Wales. Rostrevor took approximately three hours to sink.

The UKHO Wrecks and Obstructions dataset lists a position for Rostrevor, although this position is considered 'dead', as the location was disproved by surveys in 1984. The location of Rostrevor is therefore unknown. While it is possible that the seabed remains of this vessel appear in the multibeam dataset used for the Unpath'd Water project, it would be difficult to identify due to its common size and the plethora of unidentified shipwrecks in the area. As such, this summary does not relate to the locating of the wreck but instead focuses on the use of archives to investigate the people related to this relatively ordinary vessel.

Current identification numbers				
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore	IoMHER	Coflein
7058	-	-	1724	274868

Archive Sources

- British Newspaper Archive: <https://britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/viewer>
- LRH&EC: Lloyd's Ship Plans and Survey Reports <https://hec.lrfoundation.org.uk/archive-library>
- FindMyPast: <https://www.findmypast.co.uk/home>
- Ancestry: <https://www.ancestry.co.uk/>
- Geneanet: <https://en.geneanet.org/>
- Glasgow City Archives: <https://www.glasgowlife.org.uk/libraries/city-archives/archive-collections>

Database Sources

- IOMHER: 1724
- Coflein: 274868
- UKHO: 7058, Wrecks and Obstructions data set, 2024
- Wrecksite: SS Rostrevor [+1917] <https://www.wrecksite.eu/wreck.aspx?31854>

Other Sources

- Cunningham, N (2022) Joseph Fisher & Sons Ltd in Newry. NMD Museums. <https://www.visitmournemountains.co.uk/museums/blog/read/2022/07/joseph-fisher-and-sons-ltd-in-newry-by-noreen-cunningham-b270>

- McIlwaine, E (2017) Why 'C' change couldn't stop tragedy hitting shipping line. Belfast Telegraph. <https://www.belfasttelegraph.co.uk/life/features/why-c-change-couldnt-stop-tragedy-hitting-shipping-line/35381363.html>
- Tunnickliffe, N (2022) Belgian Refugees - Times Past. Glasgow Life <https://www.glasgowlife.org.uk/libraries/family-history/stories-and-blogs-from-the-mitchell/times-past-blogs/belgian-refugees-times-past>

Method and results

The key source used for Rostrevor was the British Newspaper Archive. While other sources such as wrecksite.eu, LRFHEC, and IOMHER were useful in collecting information about the vessel itself and its sinking conditions, historic newspapers were instrumental in identifying individuals related to the vessel and tracing them through time.

The newspaper article announcing the launching of Rostrevor in 1899 identified 'Miss Bost, Adelphi House, Paisley' as the person who named the vessel. Considering the general lack of women included in ships' histories, she became the topic of research and a series of questions were posed to steer the investigation: Who was Mrs Bost? What was her connection to the maritime industry? Why did she name the ship Rostrevor?

In order to work out who Miss Bost was, census records were used to find her first name. The newspaper articles that mention her included her address, which was instrumental in confirming her in census records. Websites including Geneanet, Ancestry, and FindMyPast were used to identify her as Mrs Camille Marie Bost (née De Patoul), born in Belgium in 1864 to Alphonse De Patoul and Constance Van den Schriek. Camille married WD Ashton Bost in 1883 who was Glaswegian. He was a partner in the Cartvale Chemical Company, Paisley. Camille moved to live in Paisley with Ashton and had three children. Further records noted her as hosting Belgian refugees during the First World War at an address in Glasgow. She died in the south of France in 1938.

To determine her relationship with the maritime industry, further searches of the British Newspaper Archive were undertaken to see if Miss Bost appeared anywhere else. This revealed that she named at least two other vessels, built by John Fullerton & Company, Paisley and so it was concluded that her connection to the maritime industry was via the shipbuilders rather than those commissioning the ships. This led to an investigation of the relationship between the Bost family and John Fullerton & Company. Further newspaper and census searches showed that the Bost and Fullerton residences were, in 1898, a short walk from one another. Additionally, in 1901 both the Cartvale Chemical Company and John Fullerton & Co were listed as signatories of a petition to the local council to withdraw their opposition to the Clyde Valley Electric Power Bill which would see new electric mains laid in Paisley. While little can be concluded from this information, it could be inferred that both families were of a similar class, potentially moving in similar local social circles. Additional newspaper searches revealed that at least one other Paisley woman was invited to name a vessel for John Fullerton & Co.; in 1897, a Miss Donald of 5 Gauze Street, Paisley named the Cloughmore, another vessel for Joseph Fisher & Co. 'Miss Donald' was likely Mrs Ellen Donald, wife of Hugh C Donald, a surgeon. It may have been that local women (of a certain class) were invited to name ships for John Fullerton & Co.

While it is unknown why Camille was asked to name the ship, the naming conventions used for vessels owned by Joseph Fisher & Sons shipping company make clear why she chose Rostrevor. Joseph Fisher & Sons were developing a large fleet, starting with the Kilkeel in 1892. Until 1905, their ships were named after places around Newry, where the company was based. Vessel names included Seapoint, Rostrevor, Cloughmore, Portadown, and Clonallon. After 1905, new ships were generally named after trees, including Bamboo, Broom, Ebony, Opepe, Poplar, Mango and Walnut.

Discussion

This case study demonstrates how archives can be used to meet a key aim of the Unpath'd Waters project: to identify potential for new and engaging narratives from maritime archives. This case study illustrates that although the building, operation, and loss of Rostrevor is a relatively unremarkable story in the wider context of Irish Sea maritime history, archives can be used to draw out intriguing tidbits about people, rather than just objects. The research into the human stories behind Rostrevor may raise more questions than it answers, but in doing so, demonstrates the range of information available about a subject. Although naturally the research hit dead ends at various points, there was often another interesting and related thread to pick up. This case study shows the value of 'thinking outside of the box' when researching, illustrating the fascinating routes of study that can be generated from seemingly run-of-the-mill events.

A key drawback of the research methods used for this case study is lack of free access. To undertake this research, sites with paywalls such as Ancestry and FindMyPast were used to access census data that was instrumental in identifying individuals and tracing them through history. Paywalls can be barriers to research due to high subscription costs. However, it must be noted that public libraries often offer free access to these sites.

e) RFA Industry: the wreck that never was (Sarah Saunderson)

Overview

SS Industry, was built in 1901 by W. Beardmore & Co., Glasgow in 1901 and was originally named Glasgow. A British steamer purchased by the Admiralty for a store carrier which became a Royal Fleet Auxiliary (RFA) in 1914 and renamed industry.

On October 18th, 1918, Industry was travelling from Kingstown to Belfast under the escort of the armed trawler Persian Empire when it was torpedoed and sunk near Strangford Light Buoy by the German submarine UB-92 (or UB-94). RFA Industry was built of steel, screw-propelled (with a single propeller) and schooner rigged, with two masts (Cotswold Archaeology 2015). It is listed in the 1918 Mercantile Navy list (p. 272). Its length was 59.7m, breadth 9.1m, tonnage 497/1460 and lies at a depth of 82m (Wrecksite). This ship is not listed in the Lloyds Shipping or Heritage Register under its original name of Glasgow or later name of Industry.

There are two UKHO numbers and two different positions recorded for RFA Industry.

Current identification numbers:		
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore
5091 (probably)	SWR109	323109 (possibly)
5088	SWR110	323112 (probably)

RFA Industry - Part 1/2: missing in action

The purpose of this two-part case study for RFA Industry is to demonstrate the variations and misinformation that can occur within sources. There can be 'side' issues which become apparent when interrogating collections in the process of identifying identify vessels.

Part 1 looks at widespread errors regarding the number of lives lost on RFA Industry. The figure varies between six and twenty-one depending on the source consulted. This research has confirmed that there were twenty-one lives lost on RFA Industry. No resource has been identified which has the correct number of casualties or names all the casualties in one place for this vessel.

Archive Sources

- Lloyd's Register Foundation <https://hec.lrfoundation.org.uk/archive-library/online-catalogue#search-sec>
- [Lloyd's Register of Shipping 1901 Steamers: https://archive.org/details/HECROSS1901/page/n329/mode/2up](https://archive.org/details/HECROSS1901/page/n329/mode/2up)
- The National Archives: Registry of Shipping and Seamen: Transcripts and Transactions, Series IV, Closed Registries. Ship Industry, official number: 138989. BT110/331/39
- The National Archives: BULAS - Stephens, Patrick 1988, British vessels lost at sea 1914-1918 and 1939-45 BT/110/331
- Commonwealth War Graves Commission <https://archive.cwgc.org/>

Database Sources

- Canmore: Records 323091, 323089
- CLIP <https://www.crewlist.org.uk>
- CWGC: <https://www.cwgc.org/find-records/find-war-dead>
- HERoNI: Record SWR071 [NI HER https://dfcgis.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=6887ca0873b446e39d2f82c80c8a9337](https://dfcgis.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=6887ca0873b446e39d2f82c80c8a9337)
- Historical RFA: <https://historicalrfa.uk/rfa-industry/>
- Imperial War Museums - Lives of the First World War: <https://livesofthefirstworldwar.iwm.org.uk/community/8096>
- Maritime Archaeology Sea Trust: <https://www.thisismast.org/research/royal-navy-loss-list-search.html>
- Scottish Built Ships: <https://www.clydeships.co.uk>
- U-boat.net: https://U-boat.net/wwi/ships_hit/7458.html

- Wrecksite.eu: <https://www.wrecksite.eu/wreck.aspx?64873>

Other Sources

- Bullen, R., 2004, Not Just a Name, Mersea Island Museum Publications, Colchester.
- Cotswold Archaeology - An Archival Assessment of World War I Wrecks in Northern Irish Waters “and the connection between this submarine UB92 and the RFA Industry has been presumed (Helgason 1995-2015) <https://www.daera-ni.gov.uk/sites/default/files/publications/doe/water-report-first-world-war-wrecks-in-northern-irish-waters.pdf>
- Dictionary of Disasters at Sea During the Age of Steam(Hocking, 1994)
- Find a Grave: <https://www.findagrave.com>
- First World War on this Day <https://firstworldwaronthistoday.blogspot.com/2018/10/1166-died-on-this-day-fri-18101918.html>
- Irish Wrecks: <https://irishwrecks.ie/ByName>
- Larn, R & B, 2000. Shipwreck Index, Volume 5, Wales and the West Coast, Lloyd’s Register of Shipping, London
- Mersea Museum: <https://www.merseamuseum.org.uk/index.php>
- RFAHA (Royal Fleet Auxiliary Historical Association): <https://historicalrfa.uk/>
- Tower Hill Memorial: via www.benjidog.co.uk
- Unpathd Waters: <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/>
- Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HMS_Industry

Method and results

The majority of sources within the *Archive* and *Database* lists here are those which were first interrogated when researching each vessel in the study area for WP3.2. Whilst official information from primary sources is repeated across different maritime history websites, so too is misinformation, as is the case with RFA Industry. In addition to these lists, unique sources for a vessel can be found through online searches such as the publication *Not just a name* (Bullen 2004), produced by Mersea Island Museum which contained a near full casualty list for RFA Industry and detail of the lives of some of the crew. A total of 63 sources were checked in relation to this vessel.

Casualty numbers

In the process of accessing different sources in relation to RFA Industry it was noted that there were variations in the number of crew who lost their lives (Table 5).

Source	Number of Casualties
Wrecksite	6 (5 named)
UKHO Wreck Report	6
Historic RFA webpage for SS Industry	16
Historic RFA ‘roll of honour’	20 (13 named)

The Commonwealth War Graves Commission	21 listed individually but as a 'unit' there are only 20 casualties listed when searching for RFA Industry
U-boat.net	21 listed but not named

Table 5. Casualty numbers recorded for RFA Industry.

All casualties of RFA Industry are known and are commemorated on either the Plymouth or Portsmouth naval memorials, as well as in their hometowns. This vessel is not listed on the Tower Hill Memorial, but there is different ship named Industry listed there which was lost on 28 October 1914 with the loss of two lives so is not RFA Industry

The Commonwealth War Graves Commission (CWGC) website does contain a record of each of the 21 casualties. Yet when searching by unit (vessel) name there are just 19 casualties associated with RFA Industry. An interrogation of the ship name found that there was a discrepancy in how the name of the ship had been recorded for two of the crew. Contact was made with the CWGC to make a 'casualty amendment request' and one of the records was amended. As of August 2024 a search for RFA Industry on the CWGC website will result in a list of 20 crew who lost their lives rather than 21, this is due to casualty Private Lindsey being recorded under the unit name "(RMR/A/949). R.F.A. "Industry.", whilst his colleagues are recorded under "R.F.A. "Industry." Also to note that when searching on the Commonwealth War Graves Commission website it may not be clear to users that a search by vessel name should be entered in the 'unit' search box and success in results will depend on how the vessel name has been input for each casualty. A full list of casualties and where they are recorded (or not) is contained in Table 6.

RFA INDUSTRY AUDIT OF CASUALTY LISTS											
Surname	Name	Rank	Book		Websites						Totals
			Not Just a Name, (Bullen, R., 2000)	RFA Roll of Honour	Imperial War Museum web page for Industry	RFA Webpage for Industry	First World War On this Day	Imperial War Museum CSV file	Wrecksite	CWGC	
Ambridge	Benjamin	Fireman	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	5
Barlow	Arthur	Ordinary Seaman	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Berridge	Victor Charles	Fireman	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Carney	John James	Ordinary Seaman	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Charlick	Richard	Stewards Boy	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1*	3
Coleman	Humphrey Parry	Sub Lieutenant	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	3
Foreman	Thomas Henry	Leading Fireman	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	5
Garrick	John Robert	Ordinary Seaman	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Goddard	Charles	Stoker	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	4
Green	Archibald Percy	Able Seaman	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	4
Jones	John Alfred	Stoker	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	4
Lindsey	James Henry	Private	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	3
Mackay	William Gordon	Engineer Sub Lieutenant	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
Mason	William Robert	Able Seaman	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Mole	Alfred John	Fireman	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Mole	Frederick Westhorpe	Able Seaman/Cook	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Mole	Reginald John	Able Seaman	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Norman	William	Lieutenant	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	4
Pullen	Henry William	Quartermaster	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	6
Stoker	Harold Frederick	Able Seaman	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	4
Tait	Joseph Cook	Engineer Lieutenant	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	5
Totals			20	20	13	16	17	9	5	20*	

* Private J.H. Lindsey is recorded on CWGC but does not appear on the search under the 'unit' RFA Industry

Table 6. List of casualties and sources for RFA Industry to demonstrate the variety in numbers of casualties for each resource.

RFA Industry - Part 2/2: a catalogue of errors

Method and results

Sources interrogated (as listed previously) found that in addition to errors with the numbers of casualties there were further issues with a lack of records for RFA Industry, incorrect information which has to misinformation across online sources. This has resulted in speculation of secrecy, and confusion as to whether the vessel sank, was salvaged or sold. Through this research it has been possible to identify the origin of these errors.

Issue: Lack of official records for RFA Industry

“Discrepancies may be due to the paucity of the records which relate to the loss of this vessel”

(Cotswold Archaeology, 2015, 80)

RFA Industry is **not** listed in the following digital and print sources:

- Lloyd’s Register Foundation (under Industry or Glasgow) which prevented access to surveys or plans.
- Lloyd's Register of Shipping 1901 Steamers
<https://archive.org/details/HECROSS1901/page/n329/mode/2up> *There is one entry for a vessel named Glasgow. The dimensions and shipbuilder do not match.
- Lloyds Register Shipping Casualty Returns 1918 War Losses.
- Publication: "British Vessels Lost at Sea, 1914-1918" (HMSO, 1919)
- Publication “Dictionary of Disasters at Sea During the Age of Steam” (Hocking, 1994)
- Publication “World War 1 at Sea. The Merchant Navy, Volume 3, Spring 1917 to November 1918” Volume 3, (Hurd, A., 1921)
- Publication “British vessels lost at sea 1914-1918 and 1939-45” (Patrick, S. 1988)

Ship Name	Number	Tonnage	Shipbuilder
D. Jones	2473	1896	T. Turnbull & Son, Whitby
J. Leslie	1573	1896	T. Turnbull & Son, Whitby
Glasgow	1896	1896	T. Turnbull & Son, Whitby

Fig 27: Lloyd's Register of Shipping 1901 Steamers – there is only one entry for 'Glasgow' but it is not this one.

Issue: Searches via British Newspaper Archive (BNA)

Some vessel names are difficult to search within the BNA. Many irrelevant results can be returned if a vessel is named after a country or a general term such as 'Industry'. The search term was refined to include Industry plus 'RFA', 'ship', 'sinking' or 'torpedo' but this still did not yield results. The search could be further exacerbated by disruption to media reporting during the First World War, which was either “completely suppressed, modified or at least delayed” (Demm, 2019, 10). Bullen (2000) observed that the loss of six residents from Mersea Island on RFA Industry was not reported in local newspapers until November 2019, this was one year after the sinking of Industry.

Issue: Speculation regarding RFA Industry

- Lack of an Admiralty report due to secrecy
- It was salvaged

- It was sold in 1924
- UB-94 was collaborating with UB-92 (UB-94 was operating nearby)
- Confusion whether it was torpedoed by UB-92 or UB-94

The lack of an official record was observed by Bullen in the publication *Not Just a Name* (2000, 163):

“Why there was no report at the time remains a mystery. In official circles there was no Court of Inquiry, which was the usual practice in these incidents. If there was, it has either been lost or withheld from release by the Admiralty”

It is conclusions such as this which are repeated in online sources and add to speculation regarding the fate of RFA Industry.

Issue: Was RFA Industry Sunk, Salvaged or Sold?

The certificate of registry was not officially updated until sixteen months after RFA Industry was torpedoed. A copy of the certificate of registry was obtained from The National Archive (BT 110/331). The following statement is written in red ink upon the document:

“Registry closed 10th February. Vessel lost. Advice received from Admiralty Certificate not delivered up per form 20 received 18.2.20”

Transcript of Register for Transmission to Registrar-General of Shipping and Seamen.

Official Number: 138989
 Name of Ship: Industry
 No., Date, and Port of Registry: 1601 in 1918

No., Date, and Port of previous Registry (if any): First Registry

Whether British or Foreign Built: British
 Whether a Sailing or Steam Ship and if a Steam Ship, how propelled: Steam Ship
 Where Built: Goran
 When Built: 1901
 Name and Address of Builders: W. Boardman & Co. Ltd. Goran

Number of Decks: 3
 Number of Masts: 2
 Rigged: Sloop
 Stern: Sloop
 Galleries: None
 Head: None
 Framework and description of vessel: Steel
 Number of Bulkheads: None
 Number of water ballast tanks and their capacity in tons: One - 65 tons

Length from fore part of stem, under the bowsprit, to the aft side of the head of the stern post: 196 Feet
 Length at quarter of depth from top of weather deck at side amidships to bottom of keel: 196 Feet
 Main breadth to outside of hull: 30 Feet
 Depth in hold from tonnage deck to ceiling at midships: 17 Feet
 Depth in hold from upper deck to ceiling at midships, in the case of three decks and up to the ceiling at midships: 18 Feet
 Depth from top of beam amidships to top of keel: 18 Feet
 Depth from top of deck at side amidships to bottom of keel: 52 Feet
 Round of beam: 18 Feet
 Length of engine room, if any: 55 Feet

PARTICULARS OF DISPLACEMENT.

Registry closed 10th February 1920. Vessel lost. Advice received from Admiralty Certificate not delivered up per form 20 received 18.2.20

PARTICULARS OF PROPELLING ENGINES, &c (if any)

One: 100 HP, 1000 RPM, 17' x 30" cylinders, 100 HP, 1000 RPM, 17' x 30" cylinders, 100 HP, 1000 RPM, 17' x 30" cylinders. British, 1901. W. Boardman & Co. Ltd. 100 HP, 1000 RPM, 17' x 30" cylinders.

PARTICULARS OF TONNAGE.

GROSS TONNAGE: 799.96
 Under Tonnage Deck: 799.96
 Space or spaces between Decks: 32.70
 Forecastle: 52.70
 Bridge space: 3.00
 Poop or Break: 3.00
 Side Houses: 3.00
 Deck Houses: 3.00
 Chart House: 3.00
 Spaces for machinery, and light, and air, under Section 78 (2) of the Merchant Shipping Act, 1894: 4.57
 Excess of Hatchways: 4.57

DEDUCTIONS ALLOWED: 302.77
 On account of space required for propelling power: 302.77
 On account of spaces occupied by Steerage or Apprentices, and appropriated to their use, and kept free from Goods or Stores of every kind, not being the personal property of the Crew: 302.77

Gross Tonnage: 799.96
 Deductions, as per Contract: 302.77
 Register Tonnage: 497.19

Figure 28: TNA, BT 110/331

The late amendment and lack of information in this transcript, which describes RFA Industry as ‘vessel lost’ without further details has likely contributed to the speculation which exists in non-academic sources. For example a short article on the website Divernet (2022) contains the words – *mystery, secrecy* and *espionage* in relation to RFA Industry which states:

“it was later revealed that she [Industry] was torpedoed by *UB94*, commanded by Oberleutnant Haumann, who seems to have been collaborating with *UB92* at the time she sank the *Hunsdon*”

The lack of official records, plus articles such as this which do not have relevant citations, has resulted in random theories and false news being created and circulated about the circumstances of loss and later fate of RFA Industry.

Was RFA Industry salvaged?

With regards to the salvage of RFA Industry the origin of this theory may originate with Bullen (2000 163), “there are conflicting reports regarding the ultimate fate of the ship...in official Admiralty records for ships sunk, there is no mention of *Industry*, and therefore it is possible that she was salvaged and towed into port. The Naval list has her on strength until August 1919”.

During this research salvage records were not located for RFA Industry nor in an archival assessment by Cotswold Archaeology (2015,79).

Was RFA Industry sold?

It has been possible to confirm through this research that RFA Industry was not sold in 1924. This mis-information is due to a printing error in the 2006 edition of *Ships of the Royal Navy: the complete record of all fighting ships of the Royal Navy from the 15th Century to the present* (Colledge & Warlow, 172-173). It can be seen in Figure 29. that records within the gazetteer have been merged for two different ships named Industry. The error does not occur in the 2003 version *Ships of the Royal Navy: the complete record of all fighting ships of the Royal Navy* (Colledge). The error also occurs in the 2010 edition of the book (page 195).

Figure 29. Extracts from two editions of *Ships of the Royal Navy*. Text on the left is from the 2006 edition at the bottom of page 172; the section outlined in blue is at the top of page 173. It can be seen from the text on the right (2003 edition) that the two records have been merged in error. RFA Industry (ex-Glasgow) was a storeship and Industry (ex-Tay & Tyne) was a Q ship.

This error is now repeated within online resources. A Wikipedia entry for ships named HMS Industry states:

“HMS Industry (1901) (Glasgow renamed 1900), launched 1901, Royal Fleet Auxiliary (RFA)-manned from 1914; as Q-ship used the names Tay and Tyne; torpedoed 1918 but reached harbour; sold 1924 for breaking up”.

It can be demonstrated how this information has then been repeated in the U-boat.net forum where a relative who is researching a casualty states:

“The Industry sometimes used the name Tay and Tyne and was torpedoed 19.10.1918 in the Atlantic and although there were casualties she managed to reach harbour” <https://U-boat.net/forums/read.php?23,92761,92761>

The same author also notes:

“RFA Industry was attacked (sunk?) on 18 Oct 1918. Inquiries at various sites have produced anomalous results...she was sold in 11.11.1924”

Note that the term ‘sunk?’ is used and followed by a question mark. Also to note is that the date that the vessel was sold is four years after the register was closed for Industry (ex-Glasgow), the sale date is actually for Industry (ex-Tay & Tyne). This information will continue to be repeated and circulated incorrectly.

Issue: Which U-Boat sank RFA Industry?

Whilst it is certain that the ship was torpedoed, the action of UB-92 cannot be verified due to a lack of a KTB. UB-94 is attributed within some sources as it was operating in the same area and was responsible for sinking SS Hunsdon which was travelling a mile and a half ahead of Industry at the same date and time. Cotswold Archaeology noted in their *Archival Assessment* (2015, 79) that “the connection between this submarine UB92 and the RFA Industry has been presumed (Helgason 1995-2015). A review of ten online resources demonstrated that the majority of these list UB-92 as responsible for the sinking of RFA Industry. The website U-boat.net does note that “attribution is presumed, as UB 92’s KTB did not survive” https://U-boat.net/wwi/ships_hit/7458.html

There were two online sources which listed UB94 as responsible, and these are not independent sources. The first is UKHO Wreck Report (via Wrecksite <https://www.wrecksite.eu/ukhoDetails.aspx?5091>) and The Royal Navy Loss List (Maritime Archaeology Sea Trust) (<https://www.thisismast.org/research/royal-navy-loss-list-search.html>).

Discussion

This two-part case study has demonstrated discrepancies that can occur between online resources, some of which could be taken at face value unless scrutinised. Whether it is the number of casualties, the manner of loss or the later fate of a vessel, it is vital to collate and interrogate information from a variety of sources and if possible, ascertain the primary source. The research undertaken for WP3.2 has helped to identify those collections which were most reliable, and which are the best places to start.

For RFA Industry it would be of benefit to interrogate the records of HMP Persian Empire for any record of the incident although an initial search via The National Archives Discovery portal did not find a log for the Persian Empire from October 1918 <https://discovery.nationalarchives.gov.uk/results/r?ser=ADM+53&id=C1762&q=%22Persian+Empire%22>

The war diary of UB-94 would also be useful. Cotswold Archaeology (2015, 79) stated that “online research indicates that this submarine (UB-94) reported sinking a steamship in the Irish Sea the day that Industry is thought to have been lost but it is known that SS Hundson was lost on the same day and was travelling within two miles of the RFA Industry and the

Persian Empire. Whilst Lloyds War Losses does record the loss of the Hundson the lack of a record for RFA Industry has only added fuel to the speculation of its fate. With regards to the number of casualties it is important that these are collated correctly. A family researcher may find that whilst their relative has been commemorated upon a memorial, they may be omitted and not remembered correctly in online resources.

f) HMS Champagne: the northern blockade and cutting off essential supplies to Germany (Deanna Groom)

Overview

The Oropesa (IMO or Official Number 114781) was a passenger steamship built by Harland & Wolf, Belfast, in 1895. The ship was one of eight built in the 1890s for the Pacific Steam Navigation Company (Orellana 1893, Antisana, 1893; Sarmiento 1893, Magella 1893, Inca 1893, Oropesa 1893, Orissa 1895, Oravia 1897). It was taken into Admiralty service and converted to an auxiliary armed merchant cruiser for the 10th Cruiser Squadron enforcing the Blockade of Germany in the seas between Iceland, Norway and Shetland. In 1916, the vessel was transferred to the French Navy and renamed Champagne. It was transferred back to the Royal Naval in January 1917 and to D Patrol of the 10th Cruiser Squadron. The ship was torpedoed in the Irish Sea by German submarine U-96 (Heinrich JeB captain) with the loss of 58 men on 9 October 1917.

Associated UKHO and historic environment record numbers				
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore	IoMHER	Coflein
-	-	-	1137	-

Archive Sources

- Isle of Man HER (Adrian Corkhill information)
- Wrecksite (<https://www.wrecksite.eu/wreck.aspx?136643>)
- British Newspapers Online <https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk> (multiple reports of leaving and arriving at ports; notification of loss)
- Crewlist (<https://www.crewlist.org.uk>) (Mercantile Navy List entries and locations of surviving crewlists)
- Wikipedia (<https://en.wikipedia.org/>) (list of ships built by Harland and Wolf)
- The National Archives ADM137/3696, ADM137/344, ADM137/942, ADM137/1101, ADM137/1081, ADM137/299, AMD137/298, ADM127/185; ADM137/1275; CAB37/125/13; ADM137/300; ADM137/3936 and ADM116/1613 (ships logs, documentation of 10th Cruiser Squadron activities; Court Martial inquiry into loss),
- Northern Lighthouse Board (history of the Chicken Rock Lighthouse)
- National Museums Liverpool, Merseyside Maritime Museum, Archive Sheet 14 Pacific Steam Navigation Company
- National Museums Liverpool, Merseyside Maritime Museum, Pacific Steam Navigation Company collections available: Ships, 1860 - 1978. Photographs, 1892 -

1980. Ephemera, 1860 – 1970; First World War (B/PSNC 1838 - 1982: 78 Volumes / 73 Boxes).

- National Museums Liverpool, Merseyside Maritime Museum, Information Sheet 50 Liverpool Ship Registers
- National Museums Liverpool, Photography Department (plans and photographs)
- National Maritime Museum, Greenwich – (plans of photographs)
- Royal Naval Museum, Portsmouth (potential images of SS Oropesa in the Dart estuary)
- Grainger, J G, 2003, The Maritime Blockade of Germany in the Great War: The Northern Patrol 1914-1918, Ashgate for the Navy Records Society, ISBN 0754635368
- Haws, Duncan, 1990, Merchant Fleets No. 8: Pacific Steam Navigation Company, TCL Publications, ISBN 0946378037
- Lingwood, John E, 1977, The Steam Conquistadores: A History of the Pacific Steam Navigation Company. Swale Press Ltd

Results

Essential technical and configuration specifications for possibly identifying the wreck on the seabed are given as length 421ft (121m), breadth 48.8ft, and depth 33ft; steel hull; 3 decks; two triple expansion steam engines, cylinder dimensions 23 ½in, 38 ½in, 64 ½in and 48in stroke; dual shaft, twin propellers.

In terms of visual imagery to also assist identification, searches for profile plans and mid sections took us to the Harland and Wolf collection at the Ulster Transport Museum with no results; none appear to have yet been digitised with the Lloyds Register Foundation Collections; none are available from the National Maritime Museum, Greenwich. However, the Merseyside Maritime Museum Collections have a large Pacific Steam Navigation Company Collection. Three picture postcards views of the vessel at La Rochelle were found during online searching. These postcards show a vessel with a plumb bow; counter stern; hull islands of raised 1 profile, superstructure over a third of its length reflecting its passenger function; raised bridge to the fore of the superstructure (no flying bridges), large ventilators around funnel; two masts with cargo handling jibs/booms; single large funnel; railings and covered walkways along the sides. The vessel was struck on the starboard side, in the engine room.

Figure 30: pre-war postcard view of the Pacific Steam Navigation Company's *Oropesa* at La Rochelle (<https://www.simplonpc.co.uk/>).

The detail contained in the Isle of Man HER record flagged that the vessel had been zigzagging at time of loss on a mean course N, 21E, at a speed of 13 knots. The Court Martial inquiry held into loss provides eye witness accounts from the master Captain Percy Brown; Leading Seaman W J Cox RNR; Able seaman F Murren RNVR; Petty Officer W J Ware, RFR Coastguard; Able Seaman Riley RNVR, Able

Seaman Hallet RNVR; Ordinary Seaman Broadbent RNVR; Petty Office McElliot (pensioner); Boy 1st Class Hill; Seaman C Brown RNS; Seaman C Brow, RNS; Seaman C Hay, RNR; Seaman H R Scott; Petty Officer 2nd class C Duff (pensioner); Petty Officer 2nd Class H Newton; Able Seaman John Steward RNVR; Boy 1st Class N C Whitlock; Signalmen L Cater, RNVR; Telegraphist F Deighton RNVR and Engineer Sub Lt J E Koeford, RNR.

The file includes a full transcript of the questions asked and, most importantly perhaps, charts submitted as evidence of the vessel's approximately course and the pattern of zigzags it was undertaking (TNA ADM116/1613). The loss location is variously given in sources as off Chicken Rock Lighthouse; off Dundrum Bay, and Lat. 54 17N, Long. 5 10W.

Figure 31: Chart enclosed with Court Martial documents showing the approximate course of HMS Champagne up to the moment of sinking (TNA ADM116/1613).

Within a 5 mile radius of the this Court Martial position, the UKHO wreck data reports a modern yacht Fulmar (5061); modern fishing boat Audentia (UKHO 59208), a lost anchor (UKHO 5276); the sinking location of the Maya (UKHO 5075); a non-dangerous wreck reported in 1970 by Decca co-ordinates, now assigned as 'Dead' (UKHO 5072); the sinking location of the Peshawur (UKHO 5066); three concrete mattresses installed in 1915 (UKHO 7365); World War II sonar contact, 37m in length and 10m in width, and assigned 'Dead' (UKHO 5069); a physical snag located during sweeping by HMS Itchen in 1986 (UKHO 5249); the Maja with height 12m (UKHO 5075); the reported sinking location of the Hartdale (UKHO 5077); a sonar contact 49.3m in length and 11m width (UKHO 5073); and a reported grounding from BSAC Wreck Register dating to 1989 (UKHO 5259).

The potential of these sites being HMS Champagne would initially appear to be extremely limited, unless the site might physical snag reported by HMS Itchen (UKHO 5249). This raised the question the mobility of the seabed and whether there might be bedforms which may have migrated to largely bury the wreck.

The sites surveyed by RV Prince Madog which might fit the dimensions of the wreck include UKHO 5058. The appearance of the wreck corresponds to the configuration and imagery of a standard freighter of the day with two holds aft. The catastrophic damage to the bow (possibly bow broken off) makes overall the length dimension difficult to ascertain.

Figure 32: the multibeam echosounder of UKHO 5058 in approximately the right reported loss location.

The cluster of reported losses and wrecks in this location makes confirmed identification difficult without more detail multibeam survey and ROV/AUV inspection. Overall, our present conclusion is that the remains of HMS Champagne are still to be found.

Discussion

The disappointment of not locating the wreck has been offset by the richness of the material which associated with the vessel's war time role. The seas off the coast of Wales, Northern Ireland and Isle of Man became a theatre of war. The blockade of Germany and its allies was part of the strategy which brought their defeat. The British blockade was more effective than the German blockade of the British Isles. The German population was on the verge of starvation before war's end (750,000 people are believed to have died from starvation). The 10th cruiser squadron crew from a force of eight to forty ships. The list of prohibited goods included anything arms, warships, aircraft, animals, and implements and materials to make munitions. The conditional lists of contraband which could be confiscated were food stuffs, forage, field, gold, silver, vehicles, hides, rubber and glycerine. When stopped by the Oropesa and others of the 10th Cruiser Squadron, a vessel unable to produce a Navicert or certificate from British consulate at the place of loading, would be manned by a Prize Crew and sent into port (TNA ADM137/53764) (Grainger 2003: 15).

Other documentation sheds light on the patterns of patrol vessels operating along from the north coast of Wales and the Isle of Man (TNA ADM137/120). Off the Skerries on the Anglesey coast was a convoy dispersal point where those heading to the Clyde continued northwards and those vessels heading to Liverpool made an eastward turn towards the Mersey (TNA ADM137/2603). Patrol boats and admiralty trawlers from Milford Haven or Queenstown would often pick up convoy escort duties in the southwest approaches (TNA ADM137/1300). These files contain copies of the secret sailing orders for merchant ships which advised routes that were patrolled and safer. There also documents which provide insights into the operations of airship stations on Anglesey and at Carew Cheriton, Pembrokeshire, which undertook anti-submarine patrols across to Ireland and back.

g. SS Dalewood: maintaining Admiralty supplies of high-quality steam coal (Deanna Groom)

Overview

The Dalewood (IMO or Official Number 105368) was a steel-hulled steamship built by William Doxford & Son, Sunderland, in 1909. The vessel was owned by William France Fenwick & Co, 5 Fenchurch Street, London, throughout its service life and registered at London. In August 1914, the Admiralty requested the company hold its entire fleet of colliers at the disposal of the Government to act as fleet colliers. The ship was on passage from Cardiff to Scapa Flow carrying 3000 tons of coal, when it was torpedoed on 26 February 1918, 10 miles southwest of the Isle of Man. Nineteen crewmembers were lost, including the captain. The wreck, believed to be the Dalewood, was located by HMS Fox in October 1976 and again by HMS Bulldog in 1984 in Welsh waters.

Associated UKHO and historic environment record numbers				
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore	IoMHER	Coflein
7070	-	-	1177	518338

Archive Sources

- ADM 137/4011 Home Waters Ships Attacked Feb 15 - 28 1918, The National Archives, Kew (<https://discovery.nationalarchives.gov.uk/details/r/C4115683>)
- Hocking, C, 1989, Dictionary of Disasters at Sea in the Age of Steam: including sailing ships and ships of war lost in action 1824-1962, pg177
- Middlemiss, N L, 2000, Black Diamond Fleets, pg51-60 (<https://archive.org/details/blackdiamondflee0000midd>)
- Davies, J D., 2013, Britannia's Dragon: A Naval History of Wales, The History Press, ISBN 9780752470139
- UK Hydrographic Office Wrecks and Obstructions Database
- Commonwealth War Graves Commission (<https://www.cwgc.org/find/find-war-dead/results?war=1&unit=dalewood>)
- <https://www.crewlist.org.uk/data/vesselsalpha?shipsearch=dalewood&SearchType=Exact&submit=search>
- British Newspapers Online (<https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/>)(e.g. multiple reports of leaving and entering ports such as Hull, Newcastle, London, and Rotterdam; time record set for loading unloading and transit between hull and London; collision in the Humber with SS Irwell; reports of leaving and entering ports by France, Fenwick & Co collier fleet)
- Lloyds Register Foundation (<https://hec.lrfoundation.org.uk/archive-library/documents/lrf-pun-w944-0053-p/search/everywhere:dalewood>) (boiler plan; correspondence; surveys)

- Hull Maritime Museum (Hull <https://maritimehull.co.uk/projects/hull-maritime-museum> closed for refurbishment until 2025)
- <https://U-boat.net/wwi/boats/?boat=105>
- <https://U-boat.net/wwi/boats/successes/u105.html>
- <https://U-boat.net/wwi/men/commanders/352.htm>
- https://www.gracesguide.co.uk/William_Doxford_and_Sons
- SS Dalewood torpedoed - loss of 2 RMLI crew (royalmarineshistory.com) <https://www.royalmarineshistory.com/post/ss-dalewood-torpedoed-loss-of-2-rmli-crew>

Results

Technical and configuration specifications of potential assistance in the identification process are given in Lloyd Register 1915 (110 in D) as 298ft (90.8m) length x 42.5ft (12.9m) breadth x 18.4ft (5.6m) depth. Moulded depth 20.9ft; freeboard amidships 5.7ft. Flat keel. Poop deck 21ft. Raised quarterdeck or break 123ft; Bridge deck 59ft; Forecastle 26ft; Well deck; 1 deck, part iron, part steel.

Depending on how broken open the wreck might be, these additional features may be of assistance - intermediate bulkhead in forehold dispensed with, 4 bulkheads only. 2 single ended boilers, 6 furnaces, forepeak tank 46 tons water; aft peak tank 118tons; powered by triple expansion engine- cylinder dimensions 22 ½", 37" and 61" with 42" stroke.

The intelligence reports gathered by the Admiralty noted that torpedo struck the vessel in the boiler room on the starboard side, and that the starboard lifeboat was blown to pieces. In terms of available visual material, no imagery or plans appear to be available from Tyne and Wear Archives, or in the collections of National Maritime Museum, Greenwich. Imagery maybe available from Hull Maritime Museum, but whilst in refurbishment until 2025 no contact with the curatorial staff appears to be possible.

The UKHO wrecks data reveals the following within 5 nautical miles of the loss location (encompassing both Isle of Man and Welsh waters) - possibly the wreck of the Carmelite sonar contact length 120m and reported loss location (UKHO 7395 and 7076); wreck of the Tuskar at 40m sonar contact length (UKHPO 5282); a World War II report of a sonar contact 200ft in length and with a height of 19ft amended to 'Dead (UKHO 5283); reported sinking of a cabin cruiser in 1978 (UKHO 7077); a fisherman's fastening noted on a Kingfisher chart (UKHO 7095); possibly the wreck of the Downshire recorded from sonar contact and diver sighting (UKHO 5023); sonar contact from World War II 220ft in length, height 20ft and with oil on the surface (UKHO 7394); a fisherman's fastening reported as a downed aircraft and noted on a Kingfisher chart (UKHO 5233); a wreck with length 6m and height 4m reported in 1976 (UKHO 7078); small wreck or geological feature reported in 1976 (UKHO 66632); small wreck with sonar length of 23m and breadth of 5m located in 1976 (UKHO 7074); possibly the wreck of the fishing vessel Arial with sonar contact length of 35m detected in 1983 (UKHO 7124); and fisherman's fastening near a subsea cable causing lost gear (UKHO 86850).

Based on what is currently known from the UKHO wrecks data, the UKHO 7070 appears to be the closest match. Although it is potentially larger on length measure alone, but allowance is needed for the break in the hull near the bow which may cause distortion in the overall length measure. However, there are features on the topsides of the wreck which can still be compared to range of different deck and superstructures measurements noted in Lloyds Register.

Figure 34: UKHO 7070 the wreck believed to be the Dalewood gives a first impression of potentially being too large.

Discussion

The story of the Dalewood allows us to explore coal's importance to the naval war effort. Most of Royal navy's ships were coal burning and it was estimated that these ships burned 412,000 tons a month. The best steam coal was found in the south Wales. When there was a miners' strike in July 1915 for higher wages, Lloyd George used his personal authority to broker a settlement, and the strike was end quickly. The Admiralty's secret calculations of how much steam coal was above ground (100,000 tons) and how much was in bunkers onboard and ashore (700,000 tons) reveals how close the South Wales miners' strike came to placing the war effort in jeopardy (Davies 2013: 196).

The Royal Navy's battlefleet were stationed in Scapa Flow, in Orkney, and so a system had to be devised for transporting huge amounts of Welsh coal to this remote location. Transport by train was possible to Grangemouth on the Firth of Forth, with transhipment onwards to Scapa Flow. These coal trains became known as the 'Jellicoe Specials' after the Admiral commanding the Grand Fleet. This transport by train option countered the inability of the Welsh ports to cope with large number of ships that would be required to carry such amounts and the vulnerability of seagoing colliers to U-Boat attack. Indeed, of the original France Fenwick fleet and an additional seven foreign colliers and three American-built

standard ships that the company managed on behalf of the Government, nine of these vessels were lost to enemy action together with 60 officers and men.

An entry in the log of Oropesa/HMS Champagne notes that the Dalewood came alongside to recol the ship on 6 September 1915 at Swarbucks Minn, Shetland. This confirms that Dalewood was supplying the armed merchant ships of the 10th Cruiser Squadron, as well as the Grand Fleet at Scapa Flow.

The first-hand account of the sinking by survivors is one of the occasions when it becomes obvious that cruiser rules were still being observed by some German U-boat commanders late on into the war. These rules governed when it was permissible to open fire and the treatment of captured crews, in contrast to unrestricted submarine warfare where submarines could attack without warning and did not act to offer aid to the crew of the sunken vessel. The eyewitness accounts report that that the Dalewood's lifeboat was capsized by the ship sinking and the submarine came alongside and assisted in righting the boat. The submarine's crew then gave the survivors bread, two small bottles of rum, and provided their approximate position.

Lessons learnt

The members of the Dalewood's crew lost include a range of ethnicities. It allows us to revisit the reasons why different participants were commemorated on different memorials. For example, the names recorded on the memorial to the Mercantile Marine at Tower Hill, London, are Hassan, Able Seaman; and Tamura, Able Seaman, born in Japan. Those commemorated on the Bombay War Memorial in Mumbai are Nabi Abdul, Fireman; Ahmad, Fireman; Muhammad Ali, Donkeyman; Saleh Ali, Fireman and Said, Fireman. What we recognise today is the omission and take opportunities to acknowledge the service of all crewmembers who served in wartime.

The reported loss location of the Dalewood, and where it was believed to have been found reminds us that the spatial boundaries between NMR/HERs serve as guides for record creation and information exchange between heritage organisations. Where there is a high-level of uncertainty about a vessel's final location, the loss may appear in more than one of the monument record dataset.

There are occasions when odd points of connection have been found between our Case Studies – for example, the Dalewood's collision with the SS Irwell on 3 August 1913 (Hull Daily News - Thursday 23 April 1914, <https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/viewer/bl/0003872/19140423/002/0002>) and another Welsh Case Study which follows – that of the Moyallon, which began its life named Clan Irwell, a type C S' or Coaster Standard type cargo vessel built at as part of an extensive shipbuilding programme set in motion by the British Government's Shipping Controller in 1916.

h. SS Moyallon: wartime emergency building programme (Julian Whitewright)

Overview

The MOYALLON (IMO or Official Number: 14248) was a screw steamer, launched at Paisley in 1919. The ship was 432gt, 142ft (43.3m) in length, 25.1ft (7.65m) wide, and 11.4ft (3.5m) in depth. It was configured with the machinery aft, the bridge amidships and a raised quarterdeck. Full details are provided in the National Monuments Record of Wales (NMRW) entry for the ship ([NPRN 273191](#)). Extensive historical documentation on the MOYALLON is available from the Lloyds Register Heritage and Education Centre (Sources, below).

The MOYALLON foundered on 16 September 1924 off Stumble Head in Pembrokeshire. A detailed account of the sinking is given in the resulting Board of Trade Inquiry (Sources, below). A wreck, UKHO ID 9855, was subsequently located and examined by the UKHO in 1980, ascribed a surveyed length of 48m, and given the identification of MOYALLON by the UKHO. This identification was later incorporated within NMRW entry for the vessel when the maritime component of the NMRW was assembled.

Associated UKHO and historic environment record numbers				
UKHO	HERoNI	Canmore	IoMHER	Coflein
93302	-	-	-	NRPN 273191
9855	-	-	-	NRPN 800297

Figure 35: Profile & Deck Plan for SS Moyallon, 29th December 1917 (Copyright Lloyds Register Foundation Heritage and Education Centre, document reference LRF-PUN-W706-0030-P)([Profile & Deck Plan For Moyallon 29th December 1917 | Documents | Archive & Library | Heritage & Education Centre \(lrfoundation.org.uk\)](#))

Archive Sources

- Board of Trade Inquiry, number 7817, December 1924 (https://plimsoll.southampton.gov.uk/SOTON_Documents/Plimsoll/21468.pdf)
- Larn and Larn shipwreck database 2002 (comprises Larn, R and Larn, B, 2000, Shipwreck Index of the British Isles: West Coast and Wales. Vol 5)

<https://archive.org/details/shipwreckindexof0000larn/page/n5/mode/1up?view=theater>)

- [Lloyd's Register Casualty Returns, 1 July- 30 September 1924, p.5 \(b\)](#)
- Lloyds Register Documentation (resources include Midship section plan, profile and deck plan and correspondence) <https://hec.lrfoundation.org.uk/archive-library/ships/moyallon-1919/>
- [Lloyd's Register of Shipping, 1920-1921, No.21202.](#)
- McCartney, I., 2022. *Echoes from the Deep*. Leiden: Sidestone Press. <https://www.sidestone.com/books/echoes-from-the-deep>
- Mitchell, W H and Sawyer, L A, 1968, British Standard Ships of World War I, pp.91, 94
- NPRN 273191, MOYALLON <https://coflein.gov.uk/en/site/273191>
- [Wreck Site EU SS Moyallon](#)
- [RCAHMW Ships, Wrecks, and Documentary Sources](#)
- UKHO ID 9855: Contains public sector information, licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0, from UK Hydrographic Office.
- UKHO ID 93302: Contains public sector information, licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0, from UK Hydrographic Office.
- Port of Belfast Shipping Register 1919-1928, Public Record Office Northern Ireland, CUS/1/6/1/13, 19 in 1919.
- Ships Nostalgia (<http://www.shipsnostalgia.com/showthread.php?t=13948>)
- History of the Kelly Shipping Company (<http://www.kellyshipping.com/history-company.htm>)

Results

The correlation of the wreck of the MOYALLON with UKHO 9855 was not in question until the wreck was resurveyed by the UKHO in 2019, and by Bangor University in 2021. Improvements in seabed survey since 1980 led to a more accurate survey of the wreck, and a dramatic increase in its recorded length from 48m to 76m. On that basis it was clear that UKHO 9855 was far too large to be that of the 43m long MOYALLON. A further review was undertaken by the RCAHMW in 2023 during work to update the wreck records within the NMRW with the most recent UKHO survey data around Wales. This process noted the presence of a wreck, UKHO 93302, newly discovered by the UKHO's Civil Hydrography Programme in 2020, 2.5 nautical miles east-southeast of UKHO 9855. Reference to the detailed wreck survey data held by the UKHO indicated that UKHO 93302 had a surveyed length of 42.9m, a close match to the length of the MOYALLON's 43m. Other details, such as the location of machinery at the aft end of the vessel, disposition of the holds, etc. also matched the plans of the MOYALLON. On this basis the location of the MOYALLON within the NMRW was altered to that of UKHO 93302, in turn leaving UKHO 9855 as an unidentified wreck, pending investigation to other documented losses in the area.

Discussion

The critical part to the revision of the MOYALLON's location came from new survey data which led to a dramatic change to the seabed dimensions of UKHO 9855, in conjunction with the discovery of a wreck that closely matched the MOYALLON in terms of its dimensions,

structural disposition and location. Utilising such data, both UKHO, and where available data from non-UKHO sources such as Bangor University, allows more accurate analysis of wreck identification to be undertaken (e.g. McCartney 2022), through better matching of wreck dimensions to ship dimensions, cross-referenced against historical information relating to loss location and vessel attributes.

The clearest lesson from the example of the MOYALLON is that our knowledge of an overall wreckscape, or individual wrecks within it, should never be seen as static, or fixed, on the basis of a set of knowledge collected at a particular point in time. Improved survey methods improve the resolution of our knowledge of seabed remains, identify new wrecks, and have the potential to rediscover those not examined for several decades. It is therefore critical, that as fresh surveys are undertaken, their results are incorporated into the relevant National Records on an ongoing basis.

i) SS City of Mobile (Wes Forsythe)

The *City of Mobile* was built for Bucknall Steamship Lines in 1912 at the yard of Workman Clark in Belfast. Originally named *SS Kentucky*, the vessel was renamed *City of Mobile* in 1927 when it came under new owners. At 6590 tons, this steamship was designed for general cargo and passengers (Lynch 2004). After a series of international voyages, the *City of Mobile* was requisitioned by the Ministry of Transport for use in the Second World War. On 16th September 1940 the vessel was proceeding from Glasgow to Liverpool carrying 1,450 tons of general and military stores, in addition to 35 tons of petroleum on deck (Larn 2002). It was attacked and bombed by German aircraft in the Irish Sea.

Figure 36: Starboard broadside view of S.S. CITY OF MOBILE entering Cardiff, c.1936. (By L.W. Hansen, Museum Wales 79.761/204)

Figure 37: Port side view of *City of Mobile* (Australian National Maritime Museum ANMS0418[166])

The sources relating to the position of the vessel suggest it was not sunk immediately but struggled on a distance before succumbing. Nevertheless, the final position of the shipwreck varies according to source, as does the depth of water it sank in. The UKHO designated the wreck site #5090 upon detection by echo-sounder in 1975. They estimated the dimensions of the relatively intact and upright ship based on the acoustic signal, as 100m long, 18m wide and 12m high. The wreck was lying in 72m of water on a sandy seabed. Other sources suggest different coordinates and depths of up to 92m.

More recent multibeam echosounder survey undertaken by the University of Bangor re-imaged the wreck site at a considerably higher resolution. The survey revealed the wreck was 135m long, much closer to *City of Mobile's* documented length of 136.3m and lying in 72-75m of water (MNL 1930). This survey was also able to pinpoint the wreck's position off the Co. Down coast more accurately and reveal details of the local topography and its position on the edge of the deeper water basin of the Irish Sea. *City of Mobile* is therefore a case of a wreck site tentatively identified, which can be granted a greater degree of certainty and clarity by subsequent survey, as well as understanding the surrounding area and the forces acting on the site. However, unlike the *SS Moyallon* the documentary sources supporting research into the vessel are a work in progress. Important repositories, such as Lloyds Register Foundation, have not yet digitised key information. The availability of plans and descriptions of ship features are particularly important in wreck identification as primary sources can help correct erroneous information and lend greater confidence to the progress and conclusions of research.

Figure 38: Multibeam sonar image of the City of Mobile within the wider seabed environment (University of Bangor).

RESULTS/NEW STATE OF KNOWLEDGE

Identified via WP 3.2.

UKHO 5075: HMS Stephen Furness (1917)
 UKHO 5064: SS Maja (1918)
 UKHO 5086: SS Hartdale (1915)
 UKHO 5098: SS Kafue (1918)
 UKHO 64102: SS Marianne Toft (1945)

Confirmed via WP 3.2.

UKHO 5068: SS Peshawur (1917)
 UKHO 5076: SS Hunsdon (1918)
 UKHO 5090: SS City of Mobile (1940)
 UKHO 5097: SS Daybreak (1917)

Identified via Adrian Corkill using MBES data from Unpath WP3.2.

UKHO 5235: Dumb Barge
 UKHO 5045: SS Abydos (1894)

Confirmed via Adrian Corkill using MBES data from Unpath WP 3.2.

UKHO 7454: SS Empress Eugenie (1861)
 UKHO 7390: SS Skerries (1916)

UKHO 7124: FV Ariel (1945)
UKHO 5311: SV Skelligs (1884)
UKHO 5313: MFV Denis-Chantal (1959)
UKHO 5044: SS Largo (1918)
UKHO 5060: SS Empress (1906)
UKHO 5326: FV Oona Hall (1940)
UKHO 7478: PSS Grinder (1919)
UKHO 7461: HMT Waltham (1917)
UKHO 5307: SV Thracian (1892)

Data supports existing hypotheses, further research is required to confirm vessels identity.

UKHO 7395: SS Carmelite (1918)
UKHO 7487: SS Conovium (1923)
UKHO 5049: SS Barrister (1918)

As of August 2024, of the 113 unconfirmed wreck sites within the study area:

- 25 (22%) previously unknown or unconfirmed have been identified, re-named or confirmed as a direct consequence of Unpath'd Waters research.
- 49 (43%) of surveyed sites identified or confirmed as being geological features
- 5 (4%) of surveyed sites identified as being debris or unidentifiable
- 34 (30%) of surveyed wreck sites remain unknown or unconfirmed and require further investigation

1.6 Case Study 3: Investigation of Particle Dispersal in the Irish Sea from a Shipwreck Location (Soizic Garnier, Peter Robins and Michael Roberts)

1.6.1 Summary

The likely final resting place of HMS Stephen Furness established by combining historical documents with scientific data derived from multibeam sonar scans, provided the project team with an opportunity to examine the merits of utilising other records and collections to further refine our understanding of historical events. It is known that the vessel sank rapidly after being torpedoed at 4.30pm on December 13th 1917, it is also known that several casualties from the vessel washed ashore approximately 130 km to the south on the Welsh coast approximately one month later. This study investigated whether these casualties could have been transported from the Northern Irish Sea to the Welsh coast within a one-month timeframe. By coupling a hydrodynamic model to simulate tidal dynamics during that period, with a dataset of atmospheric conditions (wind measurement from the Meteorological Office

historical database) and a Lagrangian particle tracking model, we explored the pathways of particles released at the time and location of the shipwreck to simulate the dispersal of bodies. The study found that, with a wind-drift coefficient of 2%, nearly 40% of released particles ended in areas where records of casualties' burial were found in Wales within a timeframe consistent with burial dates.

1.6.2 Method

We followed a multi-stage modelling framework to produce the forcing conditions required for the Lagrangian particle tracking model. Bodies were assumed to remain at the surface, influenced by both surface currents and wind-driven drift. Surface currents were obtained from a hindcast of the Irish Sea from December 1917 to January 1918, using the open-source model TELEMAC 8.5 (Hervouet 2007). By incorporating surface currents from the TELEMAC hindcast and wind drift data from the Met Office historical database, the trajectories of particles, originating from the shipwreck's release location and time, were computed using the Lagrangian particle tracking model OpenDrift.

Hydrodynamic model

TELEMAC-3D solves the three-dimensional Navier Stokes equations of momentum and continuity on an unstructured finite-element grid, which is well-suited for resolving complex coastal and island features found in the Irish Sea. Bed friction was parameterised using the Manning's Law, with a bed roughness coefficient of 0.03. To simulate turbulent dissipation, we used the Smagorski turbulence model (Smagorinsky 1963), which is the recommended scheme for non-linear flows. Intertidal regions were handled using a wetting and drying algorithm (Breugem 2022), with a minimum depth was set to 0.05 m. After a sensitivity test, a constant computational time step of 5 seconds was selected to ensure numerical stability whilst accurately resolving tidal dynamics. TELEMAC-3D uses a prismatic mesh structure. The horizontal resolution of the unstructured grid was approximately 1,000 m at the open-ocean boundaries, increasing to less than 50 m along the coastlines. Three equally distributed vertical layers were defined using the sigma vertical coordinate system. EMODNET bathymetry data, available at approximately 100 m resolution, was interpolated onto the grid. At the three open boundaries, the hydrodynamic model was forced with tidal velocities and elevations, with boundary conditions provided by the globally assimilated tidal atlas, TPXOv9. The model was run for 45 days, starting on the 1st of December 1917.

Wind observations

Wind data was extracted from the digital library and archive of Met Office Historical Data Record (<https://digital.nmla.metoffice.gov.uk/>) to capture wind conditions from December 1917 to February 1918. Daily wind speed, measured using Beaufort scale, and direction, indicated by cardinal points, were collected at several strategic locations highlighted by blue markers (Fig. 39). It is noteworthy that, for many locations, wind observations were recorded twice daily; however, the second set of daily observations was obscured in the middle portion of the scanned document (Fig. 40). The wind speed and direction data were converted into vectors components and interpolated on the same grid used for running the TELEMAC model.

Figure 39: Maps displaying all locations where daily wind data was available from the Met Office Historical Data Record for the period from December 1917 to February 1918. Due to the time-intensive nature of copying the wind data, not all locations were included, only those marked with a blue marker were used.

Meteorological Observations taken at *Douglas* in the *Isle of Man* during *January* 191*7*.

Latitude *54° 10'*
Longitude *4° 32' W*
Standard of Time *Local Mean Time*

Times of Observation	Date	Attached Thermometer and Barometer as read in inches or baromet.		Air Pressure at Mean Sea Level expressed in Millibars		Temperature (degrees F.)										Humidity.				Wind Direction and Force. (Beaufort Scale).				Amount. (9-10)						
		I. III.		I. III.		Dry. Wet. Dry. Wet.		In Screen.		In Shade.		Max. in Past 24 Hours.		Min. in Past 24 Hours.		Exp. of Wet. Vapour.		Per Centage.		L. III.		L. III.		L. III.						
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)	(18)	(19)	(20)	(21)	(22)	(23)	(24)	(25)	(26)			
<i>1</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>30.0</i>	<i>1013.5</i>	<i>1013.5</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>
<i>2</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>30.0</i>	<i>1013.5</i>	<i>1013.5</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>	<i>51.0</i>

Figure 40: Example of daily wind data observations recorded at the Isle of Man, as provided by the Met Office Digital Library and Archive.

Lagrangian particle tracking model

Dispersal of bodies from the shipwreck was simulated using the particle tracking model OpenDrift (Dagestad et al. 2018). OpenDrift combines forcing from the TELEMAC hindcast surface currents with a wind drift component derived from Met Office historical data to drive the advection of particles within the Lagrangian particle tracking model. A range of wind drift coefficients was tested, with scenarios transferring 0%, 1%, 2% and 3% of the wind speed to particle velocity. Additionally, sub-grid-scale particle diffusion was included, with a diffusivity coefficient of $10 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, appropriate for a grid resolution of approximately 2 km (Okubo 1971). Particles were subject to stranding upon interaction with any land boundary, after which they were considered inactive. Starting on the 13th of December 1917, 2,000 particles were released every hour over a 1 km radius from the shipwreck location for 24h, resulting in a total of 48,000 particles. Their trajectories were recorded every hour until the 24th of January 1918.

1.6.3 Results and discussion

Environmental conditions

The Irish Sea, particularly in its central channel, experiences a weak but persistent tidally driven residual northerly flow (Bowden 1980; Figs. 41 and 42). Topographic constraints interact with the tides to generate strong stirring, which is visible around the Isle of Man, south of Dublin Bay, and near the Anglesey and Llŷn peninsula (Fig 41). At the date of the sinking, a spring tide was beginning (Fig. 43). Wind direction and magnitude present high variability (Fig. 44), and we anticipate that surface currents are significantly influenced by wind-driven circulation and likely following a similar pattern. Spatial plots of residual winds (Figs. 45 and 46) indicate a persistent southerly wind near the shipwreck location for 30 days following the sinking. This suggests that southerly wind-driven circulation during this period was in the opposite direction to the northerly tidally driven residual flow.

Figure 41: Residual surface velocity for the period between the 13th to 31st of December 1917. The red triangle indicates the shipwreck position.

Figure 42: Zoom around the Isle of Man of the residual surface velocity for the period between the 13th to 31st of December 1917. The red triangle indicates the shipwreck position.

Figure 43: Tidal plot of December 1917 at the shipwreck site

Figure 44: Residual wind a period of 30 days starting from the 13th of December 1917. The red triangle shows the shipwreck position.

Figure 45: Zoom around the Isle of Man of residual wind a period of 30 days starting from the 13th of December 1917. The red triangle shows the shipwreck position.

Figure 46: Wind rose presenting 42 days, starting on the 13th of December, of daily wind observations interpolated over the Irish Sea (see Figure 5). The circle with dotted line shows an occurrence of 2% and 4% with the plain line. Wind speed is given in $m s^{-1}$.

Particle trajectories

With a zero wind-drift factor, particles are influenced solely by the northerly tidally driven residual flow and are dispersed into the North Channel (Fig. 47a). Approximately 37% of the released particles eventually strand on the Scottish and North Irish coasts of the North Channel, with a few reaching the southern shore of the Isle of Man.

With a wind drift factor of 1 %, the southerly wind pushes particles south of the shipwreck location, leading to their accumulation south of the Isle of Man (Fig. 47b). In total, only 7 % of the released particles become stranded, primarily in areas with strong tidal residuals. The majority of the stranded particles (83 %) end up on the southern shore of the Isle of Man, with 16.4 % and 0.6 % stranding near the mouth of Strangford Lough and the northern shore of Anglesey, respectively.

With a wind factor of 2 %, particles venture further south, and the wider particle trajectories (Fig. 47c) reflect the high variability of wind conditions (Fig. 46). As shown in Figure 51, particles first reach the Isle of Man around the 17th of December 1917. Subsequently, the wind shifts, pushing particles southwards. When the wind changes its direction to the west, particles are driven towards the coast of Dublin, where they remain until the 5th of January 1918. Another wind shift then pushes particles eastwards, bringing them to the Llŷn peninsula by the 10th of January 1918, followed by aggregation along the Welsh coast around the 15th of January 1918. In this scenario, 99 % of the released particles become stranded: 18.1 % on the southern shore of the Isle of Man, 35.5 % on the Irish coast and 39.4 % on the Welsh coast.

With a wind factor of 3 %, all particles become stranded. The majority (99.9 %) are stranded on the southern shore of the Isle of Man within a few days of the sinking. The remaining particles strand later along the Irish shore, with none remaining active by the 2nd of January 1918.

A typical empirical value for the wind drift coefficient for oil, as advised by OpenDrift, is 3.5 %. It is assumed that a smaller coefficient would be more representative for a human, as compared to oil, a body would generate more friction with the surrounding water. A search of historic records reported burial dates for casualties between the 11th and 24th of January 1918, on the Welsh coast (Fig. 48). This timing aligns with the scenarios with a 2 % wind drift coefficient, as presented on Figure 47c and Figure 13 in the appendix. The dispersal study showed that 39.4 % of stranded particles became stranded on the Welsh shore between the 10th and the 24th of January 1918, suggesting the possibility that shipwreck casualties could have been transported across the Irish sea and washed ashore in Wales. However, it is important to note that this study does not account for uncertainties, such as the lack of knowledge of the appropriate wind-drift coefficient, or the interpolation of wind observations, which were based on daily measurements from only 10 sites, with only one from the Irish coast.

Figure 47: Particle trajectories after 42 days of dispersion are shown for 4 different wind-drift scenarios with coefficients of 0%, 1%, 2% and 3% in plots a), b), c) and d), respectively. Initial particle positions are indicated by green markers, active particles by blue markers, and stranded particles by red markers. Particle trajectories are visible as grey lines.

Figure 48: Burial dates and locations of sea casualties potentially linked to the shipwreck site.

Figure 49: Gif animation of particle trajectories released at a 1km radius from the shipwreck location on 13th of December 1917 using a wind drift factor of 0%.

Figure 50: Gif animation of particle trajectories released at a 1km radius from the shipwreck location on 13th of December 1917 using a wind drift factor of 1%.

Figure 51: Gif animation of particle trajectories released at a 1km radius from the shipwreck location on 13th of December 1917 using a wind drift factor of 2%.

Figure 52: Gif animation of particle trajectories released at a 1km radius from the shipwreck location on 13th of December 1917 using a wind drift factor of 3%.

1.7 Discussion

1.7.1 Science and the Sea: combining data with archival research

Providing confirmed wreck identities has often proven no less difficult than it has been in the past for the Wreck Section and Chart Maintenance Section of the UK Hydrographic Office. Especially, when taking into consideration the accuracy of loss location descriptions from contemporary accounts and based on contemporary navigation methods. In subsequent surveys and re-locations, the positional accuracy of early sonar systems (e.g. ASDIC named for Anti-submarine Detection Investigation Committee) and earlier navigation systems such as Decca Navigator which remained in use into the 1990s must also be kept in mind.

1.7.2 Access to archives and other challenges

Some of the challenges for access archive material have already been described above in Visual material essential for seabed wreck identification, particularly with reference to ship plans and models, though the Lloyd's Register Foundation Heritage & Education Centre's collection in particular, proved an excellent online resource. Other access issues included the non-response of archives to queries: for P&O Heritage the website contact form did not

function and reaching out via social media, DP World and multiple other avenues brought no response.

Visiting physical archives can be a challenge, geographically and time wise. One researcher on WP3.2 lives in London so was able to carry out visits for the team to the National Archives, where particularly rich material on wartime losses is held. This also enabled collaboration with informal project partners: we were also able to retrieve information for US based naval historian Michael Lowrey who in turn supplied us with positional excerpts from scanned U-boat logs that he holds. Another informal project partner, Isle of Man based diver, maritime historian and originator of the IoMHER wrecks data Adrian Corkill provided invaluable input early on with his hypotheses on wreck ID, which helped us locate further archive sources.

Pay-walls could hinder a research journey: the British Newspaper Archive requires a subscription, and so do geology sites such as Ancestry. However the BNA and various genealogy sites are available for free through public libraries and local studies centres, though this does not seem to be publicised very well.

Particularly with reference to online sources, there are challenges surrounding copyright and permission to use images. In some instances copyright of images may be impossible to trace, in others archive costs can vary wildly from free to completely prohibitive. This hinders engaging dissemination of research.

Mistakes in sources can also be an issue. An image of the 'wrong' Peshawur (the SS Peshawur built for P&O in 1919, as a replacement) was found on three websites, including that Royal Fleet Auxiliary Historical Society (historicalrfa.uk). In this case photographs available online at [P&O Heritage](#), and at Australian Maritime Museum ([Object No. 00042041](#)) were able to prove this but this may not be the case for other vessels. Small, repeated errors can become large ones (see RFA Industry case study above).

1.7.3 Social history and the sea: deep diving into the archives

The research carried by the WP3.2 researchers has allowed human stories associated with wrecks to be explored in much more detail, rather than focussing on the wreck site alone. There are instances where the relationship between enemy combatants have been recorded in first-hand eyewitness accounts. For example, the cruisers rules adhered to by some German U-boat captains has sometimes provided opportunities to hear again the discourse in these encounters (e.g. SS Downshire, SS Dalewood, and SS Nadejda). When researching SS Medora it was possible to trace the fate of Maruice McGrath, Wireless Operator one of three crew who were taken prisoner by UB-86 in May 1918. McGrath survived and went on to live a long life and wrote of his experiences under the pen-name Desmond Malone (Malone, 1938).

Our research has allowed insights into social hierarchies and labour relations onboard and onshore. For example, the crewlists of the Florrieston report absences without leave and desertions, and instances where insubordination led to docking of pay. Contradictions in eyewitness accounts, such as that between the Master and Boatswain of Maja hints at difficult working relationships (TNA ADM 137/1517). The poignant list of Shafkhan Caderbux Khan's personal effects (TNA BT 165/465, see case study, above) includes '1 necklace (nuts)', a possible misidentification of prayer beads and hesitation in the First Mate's handwriting when writing 'Puggari' (probably pagri/pagari, a turban) suggesting he's trying to understand

another Lascar seafarer as he goes through the belongings shines a personal light on both shipboard and colonial relations.

If research into shipwrecks focusses purely on the technical details of the vessel, its last voyage and cargo, then the audience for shipwreck heritage is restricted. It is in the small personal interactions and details that we glimpse the individuals. Museum interpretation often focusses on an individual as the best way to reveal how people lived in the past and how this relates to our present day. Hence, insight into these onboard relationships has enormous potential for making maritime cultural heritage more appealing to a wider audience.

Many thousands of seafarers of Black, Asian, and diverse ethnicities were employed in the mercantile marine. Many lived in seafaring communities around Britain's coast, and their histories have significantly contributed to the cultural diversity and richness of port cities, enriching both their heritage and social fabric.

Case Study sites have also allowed us to explore difficult histories, such as the differing treatment on board for crew serving on European Articles, and those on Asiatic Articles, as well as the entrenched racism and colonialism that meant seafarers of different ethnicities were commemorated on different war memorials, something previously highlighted by John Siblon (2016) and revisited in Peshawur's StoryMap (Band 2024).

Figure 53: (CWGC/1/1/9/E/12 (WG 998/2 PT.1) letter from the Principal Assistant Secretary of the Imperial War Graves Commission to the Secretary of the Board of Trade, dated 31 August 1921.

Exceptions do appear to exist: as with SS Peshawur, SS Dalewood crew members of the 'Indian Merchant Service' Nabi Abdul, Fireman; Ahmad, Fireman; Muhammad Ali, Donkeyman; Saleh Ali, Fireman and Said, Fireman were commemorated in Mumbai. SS Dalewood's A Hassan, Able Seaman, born in Egypt; and T Tamura, Able Seaman, born in Japan are commemorated at Tower Hill: both served in the (British) Mercantile Marine however. Likewise, Mercantile Marine Reservist Najaf Muhammad, Assistant Cook, lost with HMS Champagne, is commemorated in Mumbai which shows some decisions may have been rather ad hoc. In any case revisiting John Siblon's work (2016) through the lens of SS Peshawur illuminated how archives and the reuse of archives can perpetuate the circumstances in which they were created (Derrida, 1995; Mbembe 2002), and how careful researchers need to be of amplifying this. The attribution 'Indian Merchant Service' may have been added across the CWGC database later to justify the policy of separate memorials (Fjodr, 2017), yet there seems to be no reference to this Service in any published material online other than those that point back to the CWGC casualty database. Indeed, discussions

for the formation of an *Indian Mercantile Marine* began only in 1923 and were still under discussion in 1930, two years after the Tower Hill Memorial was unveiled (IMM Committee, 1924; Hansard. HC. Deb. 27 January 1930).

The contributions of Black and Asian seafarers, and seafarers of diverse ethnicities to the First and Second World Wars, and the wider maritime world, has begun to have significant recognition (see e.g. Ransley, N.d.; Siblon 2016). WP3.2 has contributed to this research and helped show that addressing these gaps goes beyond recovering lost names; we need to confront the colonial legacies that persist in historiography and find these stories to tell. In this way wrecks of Merchant Navy vessels have great potential for further research by academics, maritime historians, and communities, to raise awareness of these issues.

Several of our case studies wrecks were impacted by the Marine Engineers' Strike which began in June 1914. The dispute was between the Shipping Federation and the Marine Engineer's Association for an increase wage of a penny per hour to a rate of 7d per hour. On 1 July, a conference was held in London between the two sides, without resolution, leading to mass action and the holding up of steamships from sailing. By the end of July 1914, the disaffection had spread onshore to repair yard leading to support action by members of the Amalgamated Society of Engineers and the Steam Engine Makers' Society. The ports of the Bristol Channel, Clyde, Tyne and Liverpool were all affected, with English engineers refusing to come back onboard at Hamburg, Antwerp and Rotterdam. Some shipping owners agreed to the wage rise in 'special cases' to keep their ships at sea in advance of the dispute being resolved – W S Millier & Co, the owners of the Florrieston, which was held up at Glasgow, took this option. There are many articles in contemporary newspapers following the spread of the dispute, which demonstrate the importance of the shipping industry to UK's economy. The importance of the particular industries has also been highlighted – for example the South Wales coal industry through the story of SS Dalewood. Industries that provided cargos such as SS Kafue carrying machinery and accessories destined for the jute factories of Bengal which highlighted links with the Jute industry of Dundee (Saunderson, 2024b).

The tone of newspaper coverage will often err on the heroic and sensational, which may obscure the true reality of the loss. The reporting style of the wartime newspaper account may be heavily tinged with propaganda – aimed at painting the German U-boat crews as 'cowardly pirates' (e.g. for SS Downshire, Belfast Daily Telegraph Saturday 27 February 1915, pg7) Conversely, some official reporting may be exceedingly brief and hence leave a great deal to the imagination. For example, the log entry for armed merchant cruiser Oropesa/HMS Champagne relating to the sinking of an enemy submarine on 19 April 1915, reads, quite briefly - '11.30 periscope of submarine sighted on about a point abaft the port beam. Submarine rising. General alarm and best speed ordered. Course altered to keep enemy submarine astern. Opened fire and after 4th round submarine disappeared suddenly apparently hit' (TNA ADM53/53766). These examples highlight that it is always important to keep in mind the purpose of the archive source, to read them carefully, and to understand what is missing or might be exaggerated or downplayed.

1.7.4. Unpath'd Waters stakeholders

There are other marine stakeholders with a passionate interest in underwater cultural heritage who also have a great deal to offer, such as sports divers, fishermen, and volunteers at local museum and archive services. The importance of regional archive services at a vessel's place of build or its subsequent home port has been amply demonstrated.

There are many beneficial aspects to developing close collaboration between the Admiralty's Centre for Seabed Mapping; the Wrecks Section of the UK Hydrographic Office; the Civil Hydrography programme; universities with research and survey vessels capacity; and National Monuments Records to assist in the identification of wrecks and to obtaining a great understanding of their present condition and potential historic significance.

Devolution and the evolution of UK's marine planning legislation, may mean that a vessel of special significance to northeast England or to Clyde and Scotland, may fall to the heritage management responsibility of Wales, Northern Ireland or to the Isle of Man. Hence the importance of retaining an overview of the maritime past of the UK, as Unpath'd Waters project is providing.

Presenting selected case studies as StoryMaps, accessed via the project page at <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/science-and-the-sea>, has created a public facing showcase for different aspects of WP3.2 research. Through these we have demonstrated both methodologies for integrating scientific survey with archival research and the breadth of stories that can be written about shipwrecks through deep dives into archives. Another public facing output was produced for the Unpath'd Waters travelling exhibition in the Maritime Archaeology Trust's Discovery Bus. The 3D printed model of the study area's seabed, 3D prints of several of the vessels researched (made from the MBES data), a poster highlighting the stories for these plus a QR code to take people to the rest of the Sea StoryMaps brought a tactile dimension to our research outputs. An original idea had been to embed NFCs in the models to trigger audio versions of the stories, for accessibility. While resources, predominantly time, meant we were unable to do this, we highlight this idea here to show how public dissemination of research could be expanded upon in any follow-on project.

Ultimately a phased approach that undertakes more detailed multi-beam echosounder surveys, diver or ROV/AUV inspection may be required to provide final positive identification. The excitement of seeing a wreck on the first since it was lost in multibeam data will never diminish. Interpreting that data and providing context for both the life of a vessel, and the loss, continues to remind us of the importance of our maritime past.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: List of wrecks investigated

Ref.	Name	Date of loss	Length (m)	Tonnage (grt)	Casualties	Cause
1	SS SARPFOS	24/02/1918	77.4	1458	2	Torpedo
2	SS KAFUE	30/04/1918	129.1	6044	1	Torpedo
3	SS HAROLD	17/05/1890	72.5	1257	10	Explosion
4	SV THRACIAN	14/08/1892	86.0	2154	19	Capsized
5	SS LEEDS CITY	06/05/1918	108.2	4298	0	Torpedo
6	SS SKERRIES	04/11/1916	112.8	4278	2	Mine
7	SS MEDORA	02/05/1918	125.0	5135	0	Torpedo
8	SS BARRISTER	19/09/1918	123.4	4952	30	Torpedo
9	MFV TUSKAR	18/04/1961	36.9	250	0	Foundered
10	SS AMBER	02/05/1917	43.4	401	0	Scuttled
11	SS SAINT MUNGO	02/05/1917	47.3	402	0	Scuttled
12	SS FLORENCE	19/09/1889	45.0	268	10	Foundered
13	TAIZAN MARU	02/05/1917	100.6	3527	0	Scuttled
14	SS HUNSDON	18/10/1918	102.2	2899	1	Torpedo
15	PSS GRINDER	21/11/1919	39.0	505	0	Foundered
16	RFA INDUSTRY	18/10/1918	59.7	497	6	Torpedo
17	SS FLORRIESTON	20/04/1918	100.9	3366	19	Torpedo
18	SS DAYBREAK	24/12/1917	103.6	3238	21	Torpedo
19	SS ELETH	01/02/1951	46.4	368	9	Capsized
20	SS CITY OF MOBILE	16/09/1940	136.3	6614	0	Air raid
21	BRIDGET ANNIE	07/11/1890	30.0	-	4	Foundered
22	SV ALICE	16/10/1910	9.1	8	2	Collision
23	REMAINS OF A LOCOMOTIVE	22/11/1857	15.0	-	-	Washed overboard
24	SS MARJORIE	15/10/1938	30.6	179	0	Foundered
25	SS ROMEO	03/03/1918	83.8	1855	29	Torpedo
26	SS DESTRO	25/03/1918	64.1	859	6	Torpedo
27	SS MIKELIS	24/07/1917	92.1	2430	0	Torpedo
28	SS ARCHIBALD FINNIE	26/07/1893	53.3	515	0	Collision
29	SS SAINT MIRREN	26/06/1926	54.3	556	3	Cargo shift
30	SS EMPRESS	16/06/1906	50.5	484	-	Collision
31	SS ROSTREVOR	12/04/1917	43.4	273	0	Foundered
32	SS MAPLE	09/12/1910	43.5	341	0	Cargo shift
33	SS NEOTSFIELD	14/09/1918	113.0	3821	0	Torpedo
34	FV OONA HALL	28/05/1940	32.1	158	11	Collision
35	HMS CHAMPAGNE	09/10/1917	128.3	5317	58	Torpedo
36	MFV DENIS-CHANTAL	07/09/1959	21.0	109	0	Collision
37	HMAV STEPHEN FURNESS	13/12/1917	88.5	1712	101	Torpedo

38	MV MOONLIGHT	09/09/1970	36.0	200	2	Cargo shift
39	SS MARIANNE TOFT	12/09/1945	86.6	2302	10	Collision
40	SS CITRINE	17/03/1931	50.4	582	10	Ran aground
41	SV TOMMI	05/05/1918	27.7	138	4	Gunfire
42	HMT WALTHAM	10/10/1917	31.7	162	13	Mine/Torpedo
43	SS CONOVIVUM	27/10/1923	36.2	152	Unclear	Foundered
44	SV EARNEST	02/05/1917	-	111	-	-
45	SKELLIGS	24/05/1884	45.0	-	-	Collision
46	MFV POLARIS	-	-	-	-	-
47	NELLIE WOOD	1944	22.9	-	0	Scuttled
48	LADY SUMMERVILLE	-	-	-	-	-
49	BESSY	02/03/1918	-	60	-	Torpedo
50	COALMAN	-	-	-	-	-
51	SV OTTO	04/01/1918	-	139	0	Gunfire
52	MARIANNE MCCRUM	30/05/1918	-	20	0	Scuttled
53	FV GLAD TIDINGS	31/05/1918	-	15	0	Scuttled
54	Pt 1 or Pt 2	09/05/1917	33.5	-	6	Foundered
55	SS DOWNSHIRE	20/02/1915	47.8	337	0	Scuttled
56	SS HELEN	01/05/1917	43.3	322	0	Scuttled
57	SS MAJA	11/10/1918	74.7	1452	9	Torpedo
58	SS LARGO	27/02/1918	80.8	1764	0	Torpedo
59	SS PESHAWUR	09/10/1917	146.2	7634	11	Torpedo
60	SS CARMELITE	02/03/1918	93.0	2583	2	Torpedo
61	HMS CULLTIST	11/02/1918	70.2	1030	46	Torpedo
62	CRUSADER	1947	-	-	-	Foundered
63	SS CALISTA	10/01/1919	37.9	229	9	Foundered
64	FV ARIEL	02/08/1945	32.9	174	0	Collision
65	SS HARTDALE	13/03/1915	105.2	3839	2	Torpedo
66	SS RINGWALL	27/01/1941	43.6	407	8	Mine
67	SS DUNGOYNE	19/06/1901	40.0	176	-	Cargo shift
68	DUNVAIL FORTH	-	-	-	-	-